
ACTIVE LEARNING FOR DATA QUALITY CONTROL: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Data quality plays a vital role in scientific research and decision-making across industries. Thus it is crucial to incorporate the data quality control (DQC) process, which comprises various actions and operations to detect and correct data errors. The increasing adoption of machine learning (ML) techniques in different domains has raised concerns about data quality in the ML field. On the other hand, ML’s capability to uncover complex patterns makes it suitable for addressing challenges involved in the DQC process. However, supervised learning methods demand abundant labeled data, while unsupervised learning methods heavily rely on the underlying distribution of the data. Active learning (AL) provides a promising solution by proactively selecting data points for inspection, thus reducing the burden of data labeling for domain experts. Therefore, this survey focuses on applying AL to DQC. Starting with a review of common data quality issues and solutions in the ML field, we aim to enhance the understanding of current quality assessment methods. We then present two scenarios to illustrate the adoption of AL into the DQC systems on the anomaly detection task, including pool-based and stream-based approaches. Finally, we provide the remaining challenges and research opportunities in this field.

Keywords Data quality control, Active learning, Query strategy, Anomaly detection, Machine learning

1 Introduction

Data quality, including accuracy, completeness, and consistency, is crucial in both scientific research and industrial decision-making. Low-quality data can lead to unreliable findings and conclusions, decreased efficiency and productivity, and costly mistakes [75, 143]. Data Quality Control (DQC) [133] is an essential stage to ensure data quality through a series of actions and procedures intended to detect and correct data errors. The growing prevalence of Machine Learning (ML) techniques in data analysis across different sectors, including computing systems, healthcare, finance, and earth science, has brought greater concerns about data quality issues within the ML domain.

Prior research has established several general criteria for evaluating data quality, which have outlined overarching concerns regarding data quality, such as accuracy, completeness, and accessibility [89, 136]. Additionally, some studies have delved into data quality considerations in the ML area and have introduced a wide range of data quality dimensions involved in ML approaches [72, 25]. However, these previous work often lacked concrete solutions to address specific data quality challenges. In this survey, our focus centered on three prevalent and challenging data quality issues in the field of ML: data anomalies, data scarcity, and data imbalance. We conducted a review of the methods employed to tackle these challenges.

On the other hand, the availability of data makes DQC a well-suited task for ML-based solutions as ML approaches are highly effective in discovering patterns within data with minimal feature engineering. However, supervised learning methods usually require a large amount of labeled data to effectively train the model, which can be a significant barrier to large-scale applications [79]. Unsupervised learning methods out of this interest have been proposed but they often

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operate under certain assumptions about distributions of data. Thus, if the data distribution changes over time, the unsupervised models’ performance may degrade [23, 106].

Active Learning (AL) [151] is a subfield of ML that focuses on maximizing performance gain from underlying models while reducing labeling costs. In the context of DQC, AL combined with ML can be used to identify data quality issues in large datasets while keeping a low cost of data labeling [100, 87]. The learning models can actively select data points that may be difficult for them to make decisions on or potentially useful for improving their performances. Domain experts will then inspect the selected instances for legitimate labels. This survey focuses on the application of AL to DQC, aiming at reducing the inspection workload of experts throughout the data quality assessment process. Initially, we touch upon general data quality criteria but narrow our focus to data quality issues within the ML domain. We specifically examine the data quality problems of data anomalies, data scarcity, and data imbalance. We provide an overview of the methods employed to address each of these issues. In our discussion of AL methods, we delve into four critical components: the oracle, the learning model, the query strategy, and the feedback strategy. We review existing work related to each of these components. To illustrate the adoption of AL in DQC, we use anomaly detection as an exemplar, demonstrating its application in two settings: delay-mode DQC and near-real-time (NRT)-mode DQC. The contributions of this paper include:

- Summarizing the common data quality issues and solutions in the ML domain.
- Demonstrating the application of AL in DQC on anomaly detection tasks via two concrete usage scenarios.
- Clarifying the correlations between the performance of the system, including accuracy and latency, and the components of the AL framework.
- Identifying challenges and future opportunities for related research.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly introduces related surveys. Section 3 provides the survey methodology adopted in our work. Section 4 summarizes the common data quality challenges and corresponding solutions in the ML community. Section 5 reviews relevant techniques in AL, including learning models, query strategies, and feedback strategies. In Section 6, we offer two usage scenarios that serve as examples of utilizing AL for DQC in the context of anomaly detection. These scenarios encompass both pool-based and stream-based AL methods. Finally, in Section 7, we outlined the challenges and opportunities for future research.

2 Related Surveys

As a multi-disciplinary study, this paper covers a diverse set of topics, such as data quality management, data augmentation, anomaly detection, and active learning. Table 1 summarizes the previous surveys related to our work.

Table 1: Related surveys

Topic	Survey	Year	Characteristics
Data quality	Sidi et al. [158]	2012	A systematic review of data quality dimensions
	Taleb et al. [160]	2018	Big Data quality management
	Teh et al. [164]	2020	Sensor data quality management in IoT applications
	Priestley et al. [138]	2023	Data quality requirements that are important at different stages of the ML data pipeline
Anomaly detection	Chandola et al. [34]	2009	Structured and comprehensive reviews on classical anomaly detection methods
	Boukerche et al. [20]	2020	Comprehensive review of outlier detection approaches with a taxonomy
	Blázquez-García et al. [16]	2021	Unsupervised outlier detection techniques in the context of time series
	Nassif et al. [123]	2021	Full list of ML techniques used in anomaly detection
	Chalapathy and Chawla [32]	2019	Deep Learning (DL) methods for anomaly detection in various real-world applications
	Schmidl et al. [147]	2022	An empirical study of 71 anomaly detection methods on 976 time series datasets

Data scarcity	Van Engelen and Hoos [169]	2020	Overview of semi-supervised learning approaches
	Alzubaidi et al. [7]	2023	Focusing on lack of training data in DL models
	Bansal et al. [12]	2022	Data augmentation techniques for improving the performance of deep learning models
	Jiani et al. [50]	2022	Data augmentation methods applied in medical image analysis
	Dutta et al. [48]	2023	Remote sensing image scene classification under limited labeled sample
Data imbalance	Fahy et al. [56]	2022	Label scarcity problem in dynamic data streams
	Kaur et al. [93]	2019	A comprehensive review on issues related to imbalanced data classification in ML
	Johnson et al. [91]	2019	Discussing the implementation details and experimental results for each study
	Devi et al. [45]	2020	Undersampling techniques for data imbalance
	Sharma et al. [156]	2022	Oversampling techniques for data imbalance
	Wang et al. [173]	2018	Concept drift in class-imbalanced data streams
	Aguiar et al. [5]	2023	An extensive experimental study benchmarking classification algorithms for imbalanced streams
Active learning	Settles [151]	2009	General review of literature in AL
	Settles [152]	2011	Outlining six main research directions which address problems for AL in practice
	Wang et al. [172]	2011	AL in image/video annotation and content-based image retrieval
	Fu et al. [63]	2013	Summarizing instance-selection methods for AL based on IID and instance correlation assumptions
	Aggarwal et al. [3]	2014	Discussing advanced AL methods developed in different scenarios such as multi-instance learning
	Kumar and Gupta [99]	2020	Covering a wide range of query strategies and relaxed assumptions in realistic environments
	Ren et al. [140]	2021	Combining AL with DL
Cacciarelli and Kulahci [27]	2023	Online AL methods with stationary and drifting data streams	

2.1 Data Quality Challenges and Solutions

Data quality has become increasingly important in the development of effective ML models. Several surveys have been conducted concerning data quality issues. Sidi et al. [158] presented a systematic review of data quality dimensions, including 40 indicators that assess data quality from different perspectives. Taleb et al. [160] surveyed studies on data management in the Big Data era. They proposed a quality management framework describing the key quality evaluation practices within different Big Data stages. Teh et al. [164] conducted a systematic literature study on sensor data quality management in Internet of Things (IoT) applications, including the types of sensor data errors and the existing solutions to detect and correct those errors. Priestley et al. [138] examined data quality requirements that are important at different stages of the ML data pipeline. Specifically, they split ML data pipelines into eight stages, such as dataset use case and design, data collection, ML building, and ML monitoring. Then they discussed data quality considerations according to stages of the ML development from different aspects of quality criteria, i.e., intrinsic, contextual, accessibility, and representational.

Other surveys focus on common data quality issues in the ML domain, including data anomaly, data scarcity, and data imbalance. Anomaly detection plays a critical role in ensuring data quality across various domains and has been well studied in previous research. Chandola et al. [34] provided a comprehensive and structured review of classical anomaly detection techniques developed before the emergence of DL-based methods. Their work featured a clear formulation and insightful discussions of the anomaly detection problem. Boukerche et al. [20] extensively reviewed outlier detection algorithms, including fundamental and advanced outlier detection approaches. They also provided a taxonomy to structure reviewed studies. In the context of time series data, Blázquez-García et al. [16] reviewed unsupervised outlier detection techniques. They thoroughly discussed different outlier types occurring in time series

data and corresponding outlier detection methods. Nassif et al. [123] conducted a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) on ML techniques used in anomaly detection. They offered a concrete list of proposed algorithms in reviewed studies and detailed statistical analysis regarding the estimation and accuracy of ML models. On the other hand, Chalapathy and Chawla [32] centered their review on DL-based anomaly detection algorithms. Their work aimed at a broad scope of deep anomaly detection applications, such as intrusion detection, fraud detection, and malware detection. They provided a deep analysis of proposed models, classified based on the availability of labels and training objectives. Unlike Chalapathy and Chawla [32]’s work, Pang et al. [130] paid more attention to the problem nature and challenges of current deep detection methods. They presented the main problem complexities faced by all detection methods, such as unknownness and heterogeneous anomaly classes, as well as unsolved challenges, such as low anomaly detection recall rate and noise-resilient anomaly detection. Schmidl et al. [147] conducted an empirical study on detecting anomalous subsequences in time series data. They evaluated 71 anomaly detection algorithms from different domains on 976 time series datasets. Additionally, they provided a concise overview of the techniques, their commonalities, and their individual strengths and weaknesses based on factors such as effectiveness, efficiency, and robustness.

Lack of data is a common issue for many ML methods, particularly large-scale models. Alzubaidi et al. [7] provided a comprehensive study on the lack of training data in DL models and summarized SOTA solutions, such as Transfer Learning (TL), Learning (Self-supervised), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), etc. Semi-supervised learning methods, as an important branch of ML, solve the label scarcity problems by harnessing the unlabeled data to compensate for the insufficiency of labeled data. Van Engelen and Hoos [169] reviewed the main approaches and algorithms developed in the semi-supervised learning field over the past two decades. They proposed a taxonomy to summarize and organize a broad variety of algorithms based on the underlying assumptions and the ways they manipulate unlabeled and labeled data. Bansal et al. [12] focused on the data augmentation algorithms and techniques to address data scarcity problems. Jiani et al. [50] provided surveys of data augmentation methods applied in the medical image analysis field. Dutta et al. [48] reviewed recently proposed models targeting remote sensing image scene classification under limited labeled sample scenarios. Fahy et al. [56] focused on the label scarcity problem involved in non-stationary data streams under tight time and memory constraints. They discussed change-adaptive approaches in both the clustering and classification scenarios, including unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and AL methods.

Data imbalance is a prevalent problem in classification tasks. There exist numerous surveys dedicated to data imbalance problems and their solutions [93, 91, 45, 156, 173]. Kaur et al. [93] conducted a comprehensive review focusing on imbalanced data classification in ML, encompassing various real-world applications. Johnson et al. [91] directed their attention to data imbalance challenges specifically in DL techniques. Their review delved into implementation details and experimental results of the studies, providing valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the reviewed approaches. Devi et al. [45] focused on undersampling techniques to address data imbalance issues, while Sharma et al. [156] concentrated on oversampling solutions. Wang et al. [173] presented a survey of research progress on class imbalance problems in online learning scenarios, particularly considering concept drift in class-imbalanced data streams. Their study included in-depth experiments aimed at gaining insights into effectively handling concept drift in online learning when dealing with class imbalance. Aguiar et al. [5] conducted an extensive experimental study to evaluate 24 SOTA data stream classification algorithms on 515 imbalanced data streams, covering both binary and multi-class classification.

2.2 Active Learning

Active Learning (AL) aims at reducing labeling costs by actively selecting the most useful instances from an unlabeled data set for labeling. It has been applied in various domains, including computer vision and natural language processing [140]. Settles [151] provided a general survey of AL and its related research areas, covering different query strategies studied until 2009. Later in 2011, Settles [152] outlined six main research directions that address problems for AL in practice, each representing the situation where a common assumption about AL is violated. Wang et al. [172] reviewed AL methods in two application domains, image/video annotation and content-based image retrieval, analyzing existing query strategies and classification models. They categorized the reviewed query strategies used in the context of multimedia annotation and retrieval into five criteria: risk reduction, uncertainty, diversity, density, and relevance. Fu et al. [63] categorized AL query strategies into two groups: based on instance Independent and Identically Distributed (IID) assumption and based on instance correlations. They also addressed the issue of evaluating the utility of selected instances under each instance-selection paradigm. Aggarwal et al. [3] provided an overarching survey of AL methods, remarkably, these for dependency-oriented data types such as sequences and graphs as well as advanced AL approaches that have been developed in different scenarios such as feature-based learning, multi-instance AL and multi-task AL. Kumar and Gupta [99] reviewed a wide range of AL query strategies with comprehensive details, including mathematical and empirical evaluations. Additionally, it discussed the relaxed assumptions for AL methods in a realistic environment. Ren et al. [140] focused on deep AL, the research that attempts to combine AL with DL to maximize the model performance while minimizing the labeling cost. They utilized a formal classification method

for the existing work and analyzed the development of deep AL from an application perspective. Cacciarelli and Kuhlaci [27] were primarily concerned with online AL, which aims to select the most informative observations from data streams in real time. They reviewed various classification approaches operating with both stationary and drifting data streams.

Although all aforementioned surveys provide in-depth overviews for their specific domains, to our best knowledge, this is the first survey discussing detecting and solving data quality issues using AL methods, which suggests a potential prospect for solving data quality challenges in the Big Data era.

3 Survey Methodology

This survey aims to investigate the exploitation of AL in DQC systems. We decompose the topic of interest into the following research questions, which will be answered via a literature review:

- RQ1: What are the common data quality issues and tackling methods in ML field?
- RQ2: What is the current status of AL research related to data quality issue detection?
- RQ3: How to achieve data quality issues detection using pool-based AL methods?
- RQ4: How to achieve data quality issues detection using stream-based AL methods?
- RQ5: What are the challenges and opportunities for future research?

The survey process consists of three main parts: database selection, literature search, and literature study. We choose Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, Springer Link, Scopus preview, and ScienceDirect as the databases to search for relevant articles. To identify articles discussing data quality control, we use keywords such as “data quality assessment”, “data quality improvement” and “data quality evaluation”. For the application of AL to data quality control, we initially used keywords like “active learning” and “data quality issue detection” but found limited relevant studies. After experimenting, we discovered that data quality issue detection was closely related to anomaly detection and human-in-the-loop methods. Therefore, we refined our keywords to “active learning”, “human-in-the-loop”, “data quality” and “anomaly detection”. Additionally, we use synonyms and alternative spellings for each keyword to broaden the search results. The search terms are combined using Boolean ANDs and ORs to ensure comprehensive coverage in the search process.

Table 2: Keywords used for searching related articles.

Keyword	Alternative terms
machine learning imbalance	deep learning, reinforcement learning, neural network data imbalance, training data imbalance, imbalance problem
scarcity improvement evaluate	data scarcity, lack of data augmentation, improve, enhance assessment, evaluation, determine
generative adversarial networks active learning	GAN, adversarial networks, generator and discriminator machine learning, supervised, unsupervised, stream-based, pool-based
human-in-the-loop	iterative machine learning, expert feedback, oracle (human)
data quality anomaly detection	data quality control, dirty data outlier detection, anomaly data

We assess the relevance of chosen articles by manually reviewing their titles and abstracts. During the literature study phase, our focus is on addressing the research questions we have formulated. Therefore, we adopt an iterative approach to expand the corpus of the study and update our findings accordingly. As a result, we identify 193 publications that are pertinent to our research and present the analysis results in the remaining sections of this paper.

4 Data Quality Challenges and Solutions in ML Field

4.1 Data Quality Challenges

4.1.1 From General Data Quality Criteria to ML Data Quality Challenges

Data Quality Control (DQC) is the process of monitoring and evaluating data accuracy, completeness, and consistency to ensure it meets intended purposes. The primary task in DQC is defining data quality criteria and detecting records that fail to satisfy requirements. Previous work has provided a variety of general metrics for assessing the quality of data in businesses and organizations. ISO/IEC 25012 [89] outlined five fundamental data quality dimensions: *accuracy*, *completeness*, *consistency*, *credibility*, and *currentness*. Pipino et al. [136] introduced a more extensive set of data quality dimensions, including 16 metrics such as *accessibility*, *concise representation* and *free-of-error*. However, these criteria are primarily designed from the perspective of data producers, which can result in a misalignment of expectations between different stakeholders. Consequently, effective DQC pipelines must take into account the data quality challenges commonly encountered by data consumers. With the ubiquitous adoption of ML methods in data analysis tasks, it has become essential to incorporate ML-specific requirements into DQC processes. This integration can enhance the value of data products by ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of the ML solutions derived from them [103]. Moreover, current ML methods tend to face peculiar data quality challenges that may not violate general quality protocols but significantly impact the performances of underlying models [165, 11]. For instance, DL methods, when employed in a supervised learning paradigm, demand a large quantity of labeled data, where data scarcity becomes a major quality problem.

Gudivada et al. [72] proposed 19 data quality dimensions for the Big Data and ML contexts, including *data governance*, *data integrity*, *outliers*, *feature extraction*, and etc. While the proposed criteria encompass a wide range of aspects, such as metadata administration (e.g., data governance and specifications), inherent dataset characteristics (e.g., data integrity and consistency), and social implications (e.g., gender bias), they serve as a high-level data quality management reference, rather than quantifiable metrics. In contrast, Budach et al. [25] mathematically defined six data quality dimensions, i.e., *consistent representation*, *completeness*, *feature accuracy*, *target accuracy*, *uniqueness* and *target class balance*. They experimentally studied the impacts of these quality issues on 15 algorithms from three ML tasks: classification, regression, and clustering. The experimental results suggested that completeness and feature accuracy can significantly influence model performances for all three tasks. For classification tasks, the target accuracy also manifested a high effect on classifiers. Completeness denotes the ratio of non-missing values while feature accuracy represents to which extent the data deviates from its actual values. The target accuracy dimension measures the deviation of the target feature (a class/label in classification tasks or a numeric value in regression tasks) to its ground truth value. It is closely related to label noise issues [60]. Besides, the target class balance was shown to have moderate influences on both classification and regression tasks.

4.1.2 DQC Solutions for ML Data Quality Challenges

The Big Data challenges, such as high data volume and velocity, invalidate manual DQC procedures. Automated/semi-automated DQC approaches have been developed in the past years to detect and resolve data quality issues. Table 3 summarized common data quality challenges in the ML area and corresponding solutions. In this article, we will elaborate on three ML data quality issues, i.e., **data anomaly**, **data scarcity**, and **data imbalance** and briefly review the other data quality problems.

Table 3: Common data quality challenges and DQC solutions in the ML domain.

Quality issue	DQC solutions
Data anomaly	Anomaly/outlier detection [34, 32]
Data scarcity	Data generation [59, 113]
Data imbalance	Oversampling [156], undersampling [45], data generation [145]
Missing values	Deletion, imputation [166]
Duplicate data	Duplicate record detection [51]
Label noise	Label noise cleaning [60]
Data Bias	Fairness Pre-processing [127]

Anomalies, or outliers, are a prevalent and significant issue jeopardizing data quality. Although there is no widely accepted formal definition of outliers, Hawkins’ definition [84] captures the essence of the concept: “An outlier is an observation which deviates so much from other observations as to arouse suspicions that it was generated by a different mechanism”. Anomalies are important indicators of erroneous observations resulting from various factors,

such as sensor malfunction, transmission errors, and incorrect operations. Correcting or removing these data instances to improve the dataset quality is generally advisable.

Data scarcity problem arises when a dataset does not contain sufficient data for training a ML model. Unlike data anomaly, data scarcity is a model-specific data quality problem. Some ML methods can work with a handful of data, such as K-nearest Neighbor (kNN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM), while others require enormous data to optimize, e.g., large-scale Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). Besides, abundant data can significantly improve model accuracy, and using a larger dataset may be more effective than developing new algorithms [11, 79]. This issue can be alleviated by improving the learning process, such as transfer learning and self-supervised learning [50], or creating more data using data generation and augmentation techniques [12].

An *imbalanced dataset* has an unequal number of samples belonging to different classes. It is a prevailing challenge for classification algorithms, especially for those that prioritize overall classification accuracy. Such algorithms tend to focus on the majority class and perform badly when classifying minority samples. The degradation degree of model performance is associated with the severeness of data imbalance [165], but it is difficult to draw definitive conclusions [177]. A common solution is to create a balanced dataset before building the model. Another way is to design sophisticated metrics when evaluating the model performance.

Other data quality problems may also occur in ML tasks. The *missing values* problem is associated with the *completeness* quality criterion and can cause loss of efficiency or failure in ML models. Two widely adopted approaches to handle missing values are data deleting and imputation [166]. *Duplicate data* often appear in databases where different or multiple records that refer to one unique real-world entity or object exist simultaneously. Elmagarmid et al. [51] provides an overview of various duplicate record detection methods that have been studied. One particularly tricky data quality problem involved in supervised learning methods is *label noise* as the correctness of data labels is typically a fundamental assumption for ML algorithms. On the data level, label noise cleaning approaches, including using measures and thresholds, KNN-based methods, and graph-based methods, have been proposed [60] to detect the mislabeled instances. *Data bias* refers to the deficiency of data that might result in prejudiced decisions based on demographic features such as race, sex, and so forth. It often comes along with the data imbalance problem when minority classes that are under-represented by ML models have equal significance as the majority classes. It is also relevant to the fairness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications [116]. Fairness pre-processing techniques have been developed to eliminate the biases in data [127].

The DQC process can be broken down into specific tasks and tackled using ML methods based on the data quality issues under consideration. Aimed at the three selected quality challenges, we reviewed three directions of research for enhancing data quality, i.e., anomaly detection, data generation, and class balancing.

4.2 Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection (or outlier detection) recognizes anomalies within provided datasets, which may be caused by equipment malfunction or unusual events and is an important way to enhance the quality of data. It has been studied for decades with significant advances [34, 22, 16, 32]. *Statistical outlier detection* methods rely on statistical metrics of samples to identify outliers and were the earliest algorithms used for outlier detection [85]. Afterward, ML-based approaches have been developed. The *distribution-based* approach [13], which initially appeared in statistics, requires the dataset to conform to a certain distribution and exploits inconsistency testing based on the distribution model to identify outliers. However, this approach is inadequate for high-dimensional data. To address this issue, Knox and Ng [96] introduced a *distance-based* approach that distinguishes outliers based on their distances from other data points. This method can effectively handle outlier detection in large datasets with more than five dimensions but has high time complexity. Another family of methods is *clustering-based*, which first divides the dataset into different clusters and then determines outliers as samples that do not belong to any cluster. The *density-based* approach employs density to identify local outliers. Samples within a given range are used to determine the “density” of a sample and the outliers are recognized as those of low data density. We will introduce related techniques presented in previous work.

4.2.1 Statistical Outlier Detection Approaches

These methods usually leverage the statistics of examined samples, such as Z value and sample product-moment correlation coefficient, to determine outliers. When identifying outliers, they utilize tools such as thresholds, informal box plots and influence functions. One important line of work is Statistical Process Control (SPC), a methodology used in manufacturing and quality control that relies on statistical techniques to ensure that processes are operating within specified limits. Montgomery [119] provided a broad overview of SPC approaches in quality control. The basic SPC comprises seven useful problem-solving tools to reduce variability and monitor the process performance, which include histogram or stem-and-leaf plot, check sheet, Pareto chart, and more. Zheng et al. [188] have applied

SPC to time series anomaly detection, In the context of SPC, time series that stay in a state of statistical control are called in-control data (normal data), otherwise, are called out-of-control data (anomaly). They use control charts, which comprise statistics of the sample’s quality measurements, mean, upper control limits, and lower control limits, to determine if a data instance is an outlier or not.

Another branch of studies is Change Point Detection (CPD), which detects a change (“disorder”) in the state of a time process, usually from “normal” to “abnormal”, have also been applied in anomaly detection. Lai [101] introduced a wide variety of sequential detection procedures and their underlying principles from a statistical perspective, e.g., Shewhart’s \bar{X} -chart, Shiryaev-Roberts Charts, Cumulative Sum, Combined Shewhart-Cumulative Sum Charts, and others. Aminikhanghahi and Cook [8] reviewed and compared CPD methods that have been proposed for time series data, spanning a wide range of real-world applications, e.g., medical condition monitoring and climate change detection. They categorized the reviewed CPD approaches into supervised and unsupervised. For supervised methods, the CPD problem can be simply cast to binary or multi-class classification. For unsupervised methods, they further divided them into subgroups such as likelihood ratio, subspace model and probabilistic methods. Tartakovsky et al. [163] utilized the ShiryaevRoberts procedure as the changepoint detector to enable rapid anomaly detection in computer network traffic. They represented the time series data as a sequence of independent random observations of which probability distributions had changed during the monitoring period. The goal was to locate the time point where the data change their statistical profile using as few observations as possible following the changepoint, subject to a tolerable limit on the risk of making a false detection. Their approach has no computational complexity and is easy to implement, suitable for simple change detection problems where densities are known.

4.2.2 Clustering-based Approaches

The clustering-based methods identify outliers based on the relationship between data points and clusters. If a data point belongs to a small, sparse cluster, it may be considered an outlier [2]. Additionally, an outlier can be identified if a data point is far from all other clusters or belongs to a cluster that is considered abnormal. Table 4 shows relevant algorithms.

Table 4: Clustering-based anomaly detection algorithms

Algorithm	Features	Data type	Comments
Pamula et al. [128]	High accuracy, less running time	Tabular data	Use LODF as the clustering metric
KMOR [67]	Build an outlier cluster	Tabular data	Regard outlier detection and clustering as a whole task

Pamula et al. [128] proposed a clustering-based outlier detection method using the Local Distance-based Outlier Factor (LDOF) metric to determine a data point’s deviation from its neighborhood. They use clustering and distance-based metrics to identify non-outliers and prune them away before calculating the LDOF of the remaining points to determine outliers. This method improves the efficiency of LDOF by only calculating it on a small set of data and shows equivalent or better precision than other algorithms. Gan and Ng proposed a k-means based algorithm called K-means With Outlier Removal (KMOR) that treats outlier detection and clustering as one task [67]. KMOR creates an additional cluster for outliers that cannot be assigned to any other cluster. KMOR can divide a dataset into k normal clusters and a cluster of outliers. The algorithm was tested on both artificial and real-world data to demonstrate the ability to cluster data and detect outliers simultaneously. KMOR showed better accuracy and less running time than other algorithms in the experiments.

4.2.3 Density-based Approaches

This part discusses various density-based outlier detection methods, such as kNN, LOF and iForest, summarized in Table 5.

K-nearest Neighbor (kNN) is widely used in classification tasks but can also be used for outlier detection. The theory behind kNN is straightforward for outlier detection: it judges outliers by calculating the distance between a data point and its neighbors. If a data point is far from its neighbors, it is more likely to be an outlier [39]. Based on kNN, Hautamaki et al. [83] proposed two new k-nearest neighbor graph methods to detect outliers. The first approach regards each data point and its neighbors as a directed proximity graph, with data points as vertices and the distances between the vectors as edges. Outliers are defined as data points with no more than T (the threshold of control parameter) neighborhoods in the graph. Another method is to sort all data points by their average kNN distance and then use a threshold to distinguish between outlier and normal data.

Table 5: Density-based anomaly detection algorithms

Algorithm	Features	Data type	Comments
kNN	Computationally expensive	Numeric data	Build a basement of density-based approaches
Hautamaki et al. [83]	High performance	Numeric data	Combine graph with kNN and use graph features to determine outliers
LOF [23]	Consider local outlier	Numeric data	First introduce density to anomaly detection and perform well in real data
FastLOF[70]	Low execution time	Numeric data	Remove some data from the dataset to fasten the task but also performs well
COF [161]	High accuracy	Numeric data	Detect outliers effectively in low-density regions or abnormal shaped places
iForest [106]	Linear time complexity	Numeric data	Effectively find outliers and can be executed in parallel
EIF [82]	Sensitive to local anomaly	Numeric data	Needs to perform a vector point multiplication

Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [23] methods calculate the local reachability density (LRD, a measure of how isolated a data point is from its neighbors) and Local Outlier Factor (the degree to which it deviates from the expected LRD of its neighbors) of each data point and identify outliers through a threshold. However, the LOF approach has a time complexity of $O(n^2)$ where n is the number of samples in the dataset. To improve the efficiency, FastLOF was proposed by Goldstein [70], which randomly divides the entire data into multiple subsets and then calculates the LOF value in each subset. For each round of calculation, subsets with LOF anomaly scores less than or equal to 1 are deleted from the dataset. Besides, LOF methods are sometimes ineffective when the districts of different densities are not clearly separated. Thus, the connectivity-based outlier concept Influenced Outlierness (INFLO) [90] was proposed, which considers the symmetric proximity relationship. Tang et al. [161] presented Connectivity-based Outlier Factor (COF) method, which performs better in finding outliers in low-density or abnormally shaped places. Specifically, neighborhoods are progressively defined by adding the nearest points to the current data point neighborhood set, which can effectively define domains when distributed in an arbitrarily low-dimensional data stream.

Isolation Forest (iForest) is another popular density-based method for detecting outliers, proposed by Liu et al. [106]. Outliers are defined as points that are remote from large and high-density populations. The algorithm has a theoretical basis that the number of outliers in the dataset is small, and their characteristics are significantly different from other normal points. It has advantages over other algorithms, such as k-means and Density-based Spatial Clustering Of Applications With Noise (DBSCAN), as it does not require distance between data points and density factors, decreasing the running time of tasks. Additionally, it is an ensemble model with linear time complexity and can work properly in distributed systems. Nevertheless, iForest suffers from a “local anomaly insensitive problem” on high-dimensional data, which tends to result in a large number of inaccurate regions of similar anomaly scores. To address this issue, the authors propose an extension called the Extended Isolation Forest (EIF) algorithm [82], which completely resolves the problem of insensitivity to local anomalies. However, the EIF algorithm may have higher time overhead when predicting medium and high-dimensional data due to the need for vector point multiplication operations in isolation calculations on each node of the extended isolated tree.

4.2.4 Reinforcement Learning Approaches

Researchers also explored Reinforcement Learning (RL) to detect anomalies in time series data. Table 6 shows the features and main concepts of RL-based methods.

Table 6: Reinforcement Learning methods for anomaly detection

Algorithm	Features	Data type	Comments
RNN+RL [88]	High Accuracy	Time series data	Build a bridge between RL and outlier detection
PTAD [183]	High flexibility	Time series data	Can adjust the criteria of anomaly judgement
IRL [126]	Based on behavior	Time series data	First introduce IRL to anomaly detection and performs well in real data

Huang et al. [88] proposed a novel method for self-learning in Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) using RL, which has three unique features: it does not require a predefined outlier definition, does not rely on a threshold for anomaly detection, and improves dynamically through experience. The authors used the Q-learning algorithm to train the RNN model, which achieved 100% accuracy and recall on the test dataset and was able to recognize the shift of means, point anomalies, and anomalous patterns.

Yu and Sun [183] developed the Policy-based Deep Reinforcement Learning Anomaly Detector (PTAD) based on the Asynchronous Advantage Actor-critic (A3C) algorithm to detect abnormal records in time series data. The PTAD regards the detection task as a sequential decision-making process, which can be represented by the Markov decision process in RL. It showed exceptional performance compared to other SOTA algorithms and allowed for adjustment of the criteria for anomaly detection to balance accuracy and recall. Additionally, the PTAD demonstrated high performance not only in the test dataset but also in a completely new dataset.

Oh and Iyengar [126] focused on using Inversed Reinforcement Learning (IRL) [124] for sequential anomaly detection. Their IRL-based framework extends the sample-based maximum entropy IRL to the Bayesian framework to approximate a distribution over reward functions so that it can model the uncertainty in detecting anomalies. This was the first application of IRL to detect anomalous data, and their method illustrated promising results on real-world datasets.

In this section, various methods for anomaly detection are discussed, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. Density-based approaches are effective in detecting local outliers in unevenly distributed data but are limited in working with high-dimensional data and have high computational complexity. Cluster-based approaches are fast but have difficulty selecting the appropriate number of clusters and are sensitive to the quality of clusters. RL methods are mainly used in time-series datasets due to their suitability for Markov decision process modeling.

4.3 Data Generation

Data generation is a common means to deal with data scarcity problems. Two widely recognized categories of data generation techniques are Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) and Variational Autoencoder (VAE). We explored fundamental GAN concepts as well as enhanced GAN algorithms and their practical implementations. Initially, GAN garnered attention for its ability to generate imaginary data, but its utility has expanded to encompass tabular datasets. Certain strategies tackle challenges like gradient instability and the disappearing gradient phenomenon in the fundamental GAN framework. Others combine DL with GAN to achieve superior outcomes. Another emerging approach involves the fusion of two distinct GAN models to enhance overall performance.

The GAN was proposed by Goodfellow et al. [71] in 2014. It consists of two networks, G (generator) and D (discriminator), which compete against each other during training. G creates fake samples while D distinguishes between real and fake samples. GAN was originally applied to generate pictures from noises. However, it can only generate images from one class. Otherwise, it outputs a blurry mixture of different categories of images. Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN), proposed by Mirza and Osindero [118], allowed users to specify the category of the generated images. Liu and Tuzel [107] proposed Coupled GAN that have higher clarity and realism. Nonetheless, sometimes the discriminator and generator fail to learn from each other, resulting in strange images. The use of Progressively Growing Generative Adversarial Network (ProGAN) [92] by Karras et al. in 2017 can stabilize GAN training by increasing image resolution layer by layer.

Although initially proposed as a discriminative model, GAN is now widely used to improve data quality. This section introduces three methods that utilize GAN to improve data duality, summarized in Table 7. Efimov et al. [49] addressed the data scarcity problem in the banking and financial sectors, where datasets for predicting credit and fraud risks are seldom available due to privacy concerns. They employed a combination of cGAN and Deep Regret Analytic Generative Adversarial Network (DRAGAN) [97] to accurately reproduce intricate feature distribution and relationships between features of real data. They also suggested three metrics to evaluate the quality of the generated data. The results showed that the model trained on generated data was slightly worse than the one trained on the original dataset, but their GAN-based method can learn and reproduce complex features effectively.

Data scarcity is also a big problem in the medical domain. In the past, the image enhancement work always relied on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based denoising methods, but these approaches can not deal with bad resolution and low contrast issues. Tang et al. [162] proposed a Stacked Generative Adversarial Network (SGAN) method to enhance images captured by CT to improve the performance of lesion segmentation. The SGAN has two models, where the first reduces noise in the CT image, and the second generates high-quality images with better resolution, clear boundaries, and stronger contrast. The two-step approach was necessary due to the typically high noise and low contrast in CT images. The results showed that the SGAN method achieved higher accuracy than other image

Table 7: Data generation methods

Algorithm	Features	Data type	Comments
Efimov et al. [49]	Combining cGAN and DRAGAN	Numeric data	Achieving nearly the same accuracy as natural data
SGAN [162]	Two-step GAN	Image data	Using two different GANs to complete one task
Mauro et al. [29]	Comparison of two GAN	Numeric data	Comparing two different methods and verifying output by RF
Wan et al. [171]	VAE	Image data	Generated images are clean and sharp
Zhu et al. [190]	self-supervised sequential VAE	Video and audio data	Addressing the representation disentanglement by exploring intrinsic supervision signals
Lotfollahi et al. [110]	trVAE	Image and RNA-seq data	More accurate OOD generation compared with standard CVAE

improvement methods, and combining SGAN with Holistically Nested Network (HNN) resulted in the most efficient outcome.

GAN is also applied for data synthesis in the wireless network domain. Castelli et al. [29] used two different types of GANs, vanilla GAN and Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network (WGAN), to generate synthetic telecommunication data related to WiFi signal quality which will help companies to ensure a high-quality service and customer satisfaction. The robustness of the proposed GAN methods was verified by the indistinguishability of Random Forests between the real and artificial datasets. Experimental results using statistical metrics such as median and Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence suggested that both methods can generate a dataset similar to the original one, and the relations between features are also the same as the natural dataset.

Another line of work investigates the application of VAE in data generation, as listed in Table 7. Kingma and Welling [94] introduced VAE in 2013. The key innovation of VAE was to make the latent space probabilistic compared to a standard autoencoder whose encoder maps data to a fixed, deterministic point in the latent space. It has then been applied to generating image, text, audio, and video data. Wan et al. [171] suggested using VAE as a synthetic sampling method to obtain a balanced data distribution by generating samples for the minority class. The experimental results on numerous image datasets showed that VAE can generate very sharp and clean images and outperform the traditional synthetic sampling methods. Zhu et al. [190] proposed a sequential VAE, a recurrent version of VAE, that learns disentangled time-invariant and time-varying representations for sequential data. It was used to generate video and audio data. Lotfollahi et al. [110] proposed Transfer Variational Autoencoder (trVAE), which was developed under the Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE) framework but overcame its limitations on out-of-distribution (OOD) generation. They exploited maximum mean discrepancy to regularize the joint distribution across the categorical variable to produce a more compact representation of a cross-condition distribution, which will lead to more accurate OOD prediction.

4.4 Class Balancing

Addressing class imbalance is crucial for preventing biased predictions, especially when certain classes dominate the dataset. Two direct approaches to creating a balanced dataset are oversampling (adding more samples to the minority class) and undersampling (removing some samples from the majority class). In 2002, Chawla et al. [35] proposed Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), an improved version of the random oversampling algorithm that has become a widely accepted method in handling imbalanced datasets. SMOTE algorithm generates new samples selected by a kNN from the minority category and adds them to the original dataset to create a balanced dataset. Nowadays, combining oversampling with ML methods has shown great success in addressing imbalanced datasets. This section reviews three oversampling methods and their features, as shown in Table 8.

Zhang et al. [185] proposed a method that combines the SMOTE algorithm with the SVM classification method to deal with imbalanced datasets. They used an improved Random-SMOTE method to generate samples from the minority class and exploited a Biased-SVM algorithm to set the different penalty factors for the minority samples and the majority samples. To avoid data redundancy in generated samples, they only considered generating samples that are “close” to the boundary, i.e., with the smallest distance from the minority class cluster center to the majority class

Table 8: Class balancing methods

Algorithm	Features	Data type	Comments
Zhang et al. [185]	Combining SMOTE and SVM	Random-Tabular data	Oversampling the minority close to the classification boundary
Ando and Huang [9]	Re-sampling in deep feature space	CNN’s Image data	Jointly optimizing representation learning and classifier learning
Engelmann and Lessmann [52]	cWGAN-based oversampling	Tabular data	Outperforming random oversampling and SMOTE-style methods on the majority of datasets

center. The experiments conducted on five imbalanced data sets from the UCI data set showed that this approach achieved a significant classification effect on imbalanced datasets.

To address the data imbalance problem in DL models, Ando and Huang [9] proposed a Deep Over-sampling (DOS) framework for extending the synthetic oversampling method to the CNN. Their method aims to re-sample the training data in a nonlinear feature space acquired by the CNN. For each sample, its k in-class neighbors in the deep feature space are used to generate synthetic targets for the minority class samples, which are not only for complementing the minority classes for classifier learning but also for supervising representation learning. The experimental results verified the effectiveness of the proposed framework, and the improvements were more significant under a more severe imbalance setting.

Engelmann and Lessmann [52] proposed a cWGAN-based oversampling method that can effectively model tabular data with numerical and categorical variables. They employed a cGAN structure with a WGANGP loss function to estimate the conditional distribution and then used the generator to produce additional samples of the minority class. Regarding the multi-modality data modeling, they modeled the categorical columns with one-hot encoding and used the Gumbel-softmax activation function with temperature $\tau = 0.66$. For numerical columns, they utilized a min-max-scaling to $[0, 1]$ and no activation function for the generator output. An empirical study suggested that their method outperformed random oversampling and SMOTE-style methods on the majority of datasets, which is attributed to the specific GAN architecture developed for oversampling.

5 Active Learning

Although many studies exist for enhancing the quality of a dataset, fully automated Data Quality Control (DQC) methods either suffer from low accuracy (e.g., unsupervised ML methods) or rely on a large number of quality labels (e.g., supervised ML methods). Active Learning (AL) is a potential solution to these limitations. By strategically selecting the most informative data points for labeling, it reduces manual labeling efforts while improving model accuracy. Moreover, in scenarios where data changes over time, AL allows the DQC system to continuously adapt by selecting new, relevant data points for human review, ensuring that the system remains up-to-date and effective. This section reviews the core concepts and techniques developed in the AL field and evaluation metrics commonly used for AL methods.

5.1 Concepts and Techniques in AL

There are some surveys dedicated to the application of AL in various domains [140, 26, 4, 148]. We will briefly summarize the main concepts in AL studies and refer the users to other surveys. Following the framework proposed by Settles [151], AL features three scenarios, as shown in Figure 1. *Membership query synthesis* is the first proposed AL scenario by Angluin [10] in 1988 for concept learning. It allows the learner to query samples from inside and outside the unlabeled dataset, even synthetic data. However, it is reported to be not feasible for human annotators [14]. *Stream-based* AL approaches assume that each unlabeled instance arrives once at a time, and the learner must decide whether to query or discard it, while *pool-based* AL methods can traverse the whole unlabeled dataset and select the most representative ones. Since membership query synthesis is not applicable in DQC circumstance, we only focus on stream-based and pool-based scenarios. Pool-based AL methods receive more popularity due to their simplicity, while stream-based methods are commonly exploited when there are limited storage and computing resources.

Regardless of the application scenarios, AL comprises four essential components, *Oracle*, *Learning model*, *Query strategy*, and *Feedback strategy*. Settles [151] has presented the concepts of Oracle, Learning model, and Query strategy in the survey of AL studies. In addition to their proposal, we added Feedback strategy as the fourth component.

Figure 1: Active Learning scenarios

The oracle is able to provide true labels for any requested instances. The learning model, also called a target model, makes predictions on unseen data and interacts with an oracle via the query and feedback strategy to continuously improve its predictive accuracy. The query strategy determines which samples to be presented to the oracle for annotation/labeling, and the feedback strategy incorporates feedback to improve the models' predictive accuracy [140]. The effectiveness of developed AL approaches on given tasks heavily relies on appropriate design and combination of these four elements. An AL framework is generally an iterative process with the iteration number controlled by a labeling cost, illustrated in Figure 2. For each round, a learning model selects some samples and requests labels from the oracle, after which the model will update itself with newly labeled data. This section will briefly review concepts and techniques within the AL field, and more detailed methods will be analyzed in Section 6.3 through two use cases.

Figure 2: A typical AL framework

5.1.1 Learning Models

The AL framework has the flexibility to adopt various learning models. Table 9, which is based on Mahesh's work [114], provides a taxonomy of common ML models that can be integrated with AL approaches. Initially, AL was proposed to be combined with supervised learning methods in the membership query synthesis scenario. In 1992, Baum and Lang [14] applied this framework to a neural network. Stream-based and pool-based scenarios were also initially applied using supervised neural networks. Later in 1996, Liere and Tadepalli [105] explored the possibility of using unsupervised learning algorithms in this domain. Board and Pitt introduced an intermediate oracle to semi-supervised learning methods [18]. In 2009, Lopes et al. [109] combined AL with IRL to reduce the number of samples required from the experts.

Klapwijk et al. [95] proposed a Qoala-T tool to assess the quality of structural Magnetic Resonance Imaging (sMRI) data that is automatically segmented using FreeSurfer. The Qoala-T tool can accurately predict the quality of the remaining data given a subset of labeled data. Three models, i.e., RF, Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) and SVM are tested to find the best model for predicting the MRI image quality. The experimental results suggested a superior

Table 9: Common learning models

Method type	Algorithms
Supervised learning	Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-nearest Neighbor (kNN), Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forests (RF), Adaboost
Unsupervised learning	Principal Component Analysis (PCA), K-Means Clustering, Isolation Forest (iForest), Density-based Spatial Clustering Of Applications With Noise (DBSCAN) Clustering, Autoencoder
Semi-supervised learning	Co-training, Self-training, Transductive Support Vector Machine (SVM)
Reinforcement learning	Q-Learning, Stateactionrewardstateaction (SARSA)
Deep Learning	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), Long Short-term Memory (LSTM), Generative Adversarial Network (GAN)

performance of the RF model, with an AUC of 0.98, in assessing MRI image quality. Additionally, they found that it is possible to build a decent model with a limited amount of data by using their tool.

Mieruch et al. [117] presented SalaciaML, a DL algorithm using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) to assess the quality of ocean observatory data. It represents one of the first applications of DL for massive ocean data quality control. They used the SeaDataNet dataset [159], which contains oceanic measurements over the Mediterranean Seas along with quality flags. The deep neural network was trained on more than 2 million temperature measurements spanning the last 100 years and achieved over 90% accuracy in classifying the quality of samples. However, it is only tested on one Ocean Variable, i.e., sea temperature, and other variables, such as salinity, oxygen and nutrients, should be considered for further improvement.

Pontoriero et al. [137] utilized CNN DenseNet to examine the image data quality generated by PET/CT scanners. Two neural networks were trained for two different tasks: to assess the misalignment from a standard reference space and to identify if the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) level was within predefined acceptable noise level ranges. Three datasets are utilized to evaluate the proposed methods, with one dataset for training and in-domain testing and the other two for out-of-domain testing. The results suggested promising performances of their methods when testing in independent datasets different from training samples. However, the model performance may still be sub-optimal due to the small size of the training dataset, resulting from the high cost of FDOPA brain PET scans.

Another angle to categorize learning models is based on the dataset being processed, which groups them into online learning and offline learning. Offline learning, also known as batch learning, requires training instances to be available before the learning task, assuming that the data follows the i.i.d. (independent and identically distributed) assumption [47]. On the other hand, online learning does not assume any specific data distribution and updates predictive models sequentially. Consequently, some literature introduces online learning in conjunction with stream-based AL.

5.1.2 Query Strategies

The core of query strategies is to select the most useful samples to be labeled by human experts, thus reducing the labeling cost. They have been extensively studied and discussed in the past years [151, 99, 140]. Instance selection techniques depend on various factors, including the underlying assumptions of usefulness (which derives the instance selection criteria), suitable ML tasks (e.g., classification, regression and clustering), whether explicitly considering data distribution and the requirements for learners. Kumar and Gupta [99] have proposed a comprehensive taxonomy to structure pool-based query strategies. However, as their work was done before 2010, AL query strategies specifically designed for DL were not thoroughly discussed. Ren et al. [140] filled this gap by reviewing studies on Deep Active Learning (DeepAL), a research field that investigates how AL can be applied to powerful DL techniques to reduce the cost of sample annotation. We devise a taxonomy to consolidate different perspectives from previous surveys, which encompasses commonly used AL query strategies and categorizes them based on their problem settings and the underlying principles. Figure 3 shows the proposed taxonomy.

We roughly divide AL query strategies into pool-based, stream-based, and DeepAL. Although DeepAL may fall within the scope of the other two categories, it is valuable to regard it as a significant research branch of the AL field. This is because the rapid advancement of DL techniques, regarding both model intricacies and learning procedures,

Figure 3: AL query strategies

presents unique challenges for the research community in implementing AL within DL contexts. Our primary focus will be on a subset of DeepAL research that addresses specific challenges related to DL methods. The pool-based AL query strategies mainly comprise *single-mode sampling*, *batch-mode sampling* and *RL-based sampling*.

Single-mode sampling. The single-mode sampling assumes that unlabeled data instances are queried one by one. Consequently, query strategies within this scheme choose instances solely based on their individual information without considering the relations among different instances.

The *uncertainty sampling* method [151], which aims to search for the most uncertain instances, is the most popular query strategy in AL. It includes three concrete sampling methods, *least confidence sampling*, *entropy-based sampling*, and *margin sampling*. They are usually combined with traditional ML methods, such as kNN, LR, and RF [142, 191]. Another query strategy that shares a similar idea as uncertainty sampling is the *closest-to-decision-boundary* sampling. It was proposed by Almgren and Jonsson [6] to be combined with SVM models under the assumption that the points closest to the SVM hyperplane are the ones of which the classifier is the most uncertain. However, uncertainty sampling fails on noisier data and performs as well as random sampling for less noisy data [146, 80]. Mussmann and Liang [121] proposed two empirical solutions to this problem. They suggested using uncertain sampling if the estimated final error is less than around 10% based on domain knowledge. Otherwise, random sampling can be run until the test error is below 10%, and then switch to uncertainty sampling.

The *Query-by-Committee (QBC)* [155] approach is an ensemble sampling method where a committee of learning models evaluates the informativeness of candidate instances via a consensus mechanism. Two disagreement measurements are commonly utilized: the *vote entropy* and the *average KL divergence* metrics. For the vote entropy metric, the uncertainty of labeling an instance is measured using Shannon information entropy, considering the probabilities of each class assignment from all committee members' predictions. The instance with the highest disagreement among the committee members' predictions is selected. The average KL divergence computes the average distance of labeling by each committee member relative to the overall committee's labeling. Their formal definitions can be found in [151].

On the other hand, the *expected model change* concept [151], aims to query the instance that would have the most significant impact on the model’s behavior. Under this paradigm, Settles et al. [154] presented Expected Gradient Length (EGL) for multiple-instance learning problems. EGL identifies the instance that would create the greatest change in the gradient of the objective function if it is added to the training set. Likewise, Freytag et al. [62] proposed the Expected Model Output Change (EMOC) query strategy, which measures the influence of a newly labeled sample on model decisions through a loss function marginalized over all possible inputs and unknown outputs. The loss function is derived from the differences in model outputs. The instance with the highest EMOC value is selected for querying.

The *expected error reduction* query strategy [141] adopts a similar idea as the expected model change method but utilizes expected future error, a more direct measure, to assess the impact of a sample. An instance is selected as long as it results in the lowest error when revealing its label and adding it to the training set. However, as pointed out by Settles [151], this query strategy is extremely computationally expensive as it requires estimation of the expected future error for each instance in the pool and incremental re-training of the new model for each possible query labeling.

Batch-mode sampling. The batch-mode sampling differs from single-mode sampling in that it identifies a batch of candidate unlabeled data samples at each acquisition step. In this case, metrics related to instance correlations, such as diversity, are taken into account to construct an optimal query set. In contrast to the uncertainty sampling approach, where the primary objective is to pick instances that are most informative based on the uncertainty of model predictions, the *diversity-based* sampling method [63, 99], focuses on selecting samples that are the most representative. Brinker [24] introduced a diversity-based AL metric for SVM models, which calculates the angles between the hyperplanes induced by two data examples. The *most anomalous* sampling method is prevalent in unsupervised/semi-supervised anomaly detection approaches [41, 42, 40, 176], where top instances ranked by their anomaly scores are queried for labels. Although in theory, it can operate under one-by-one query scenarios, it has been mainly exploited in the batch-mode AL approaches. The above query strategies are often utilized along with other query strategies, such as uncertainty sampling, to form *combined instance selection* methods. For example, Marcelli et al. [115] incorporates the most anomalous sampling with uncertainty sampling and QBC sampling respectively to tackle the data imbalance problem. Wang et al. [174] proposed an ensemble query strategy that comprises the most anomalous sampling with uncertainty sampling and interval random sampling, which achieved the highest F1 score compared with individual query strategies.

RL-based sampling. Advanced RL-based sampling methods approach AL as a consecutive decision-making process where a sequence of data points is strategically chosen based on a policy $\pi(a_t | s_t)$, where a_t represents the action taken at step t , and s_t represents the state at that step. All the instance acquisition steps collectively contribute to the ultimate goal of reducing the annotation cost. Pang et al. [132] applied RL to a pool-based AL scenario, where the *action* is defined as selecting a data point from the unlabeled set. They strived to develop an AL query criteria that generalize across tasks/datasets. They developed a DNN query criterion that is parameterized by a dataset embedding and empowers the model with automatic strategy calibration using given dataset statistics by multi-task training the DNN policy on a diverse batch of source datasets.

Stream-based query strategies. Stream-based AL (or online AL) assumes that the data is generated in a continuous stream and the system has to decide whether to query the current instance immediately. An essential factor in stream-based AL approaches is whether the data stream remains consistent (stationary) or not. *Stationary stream sampling* supposes that the data stream is generated from a stable distribution. Cesa-Bianchi et al. [30] proposed a selective sampling Perceptron algorithm that utilizes a Bernoulli random variable to decide whether to query the current instance. The parameter of this variable is modified according to prediction mistakes after revealing the labels, specifically, a margin value representing how far the ground-truth label is away from the current classifier hyperplane. However, as suggested by Hao et al. [81], the margin value is an uncertainty but not a confidence indicator for the model. They introduced a confidence factor which involves the variance of the margin value of the current sample that characterizes how often similar instances have been seen by the model.

Drifting data streams, where the data distribution changes over time, significantly affects the resilience of classifiers and presents considerable challenges for AL methods [27]. *Drifting stream sampling* methods usually work with adaptive models to enhance their robustness while maintaining minimal labeling requirements. Žliobaitė et al. [192] proposed three AL query strategies to explicitly handle concept drift in streaming data. Their methods operate under the DDM framework, where the old classifier is constantly replaced by a new classifier once its accuracy decreases. Different from a fixed uncertainty threshold, they suggested a *variable uncertainty strategy* which exploits a time-variable threshold that adjusts itself depending on the incoming data to align with the budget. To cope with concept drift issues, they extend the uncertainty strategy with randomization to occasionally select certain instances. They also proposed a *split strategy* that randomly splits a stream into two streams with one labeled according to the uncertainty strategy and the other labeled according to the random strategy. The reason behind this is to allow the change detectors

to distinguish data distribution changes caused by concept drift from these by AL. Liu et al. [108] presented a dual-query strategy including uncertainty and representativeness metrics. In terms of representativeness, they introduced a *local density* measure against samples stored within a cognition window, which is updated based on instances' memory strengths, according to Ebbinghaus laws of human memory cognition. If an input instance's local density is higher than a pre-defined threshold, then it will proceed to uncertainty sampling criteria.

The RL-based sampling methods are also exploited in stream-based AL tasks as they naturally fit the stream learning process. Fang et al. [57] formalized the stream-based AL as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), where the *state* corresponds to the current labeled data set together with a candidate unlabelled data point, and *action* denotes whether the human expert must annotate the current instance. The goal of this process is to learn a RL *policy* that can maximize the reward, e.g., the held-out performance of the model and its variances. In this case, AL can be performed more strategically and collaboratively, rather than replaying greedy heuristics, e.g., maximizing model uncertainty for every instance selection iteration.

In some other scenarios, the constraints on stream-based AL are relaxed and the problem is converted to *Stream-pool-based AL*, which splits the data streams into small chunks and each chunk can be seen as a data pool. Zhu et al. [189] proposed a Minimal Variance (MV) query strategy, which selects instances that cause the largest variance in the classifier ensemble.

DeepAL query strategies. DL methods are powerful in pattern recognition and have been particularly successful in tasks such as image recognition, natural language processing, and speech recognition. Recently, combining AL with DL has received much attention since DL algorithms are data hungry and AL can effectively reduce annotation cost [140]. In this part, we will examine a selection of important research in the field of DeepAL, and direct readers to a thorough survey by Ren et al. [140] for a more comprehensive overview.

The DeepAL query strategies are primarily concerned with *how to measure the informativeness of sampling using output/intermediate states of the DL models*. The simplest way is *Uncertainty DeepAL* which extends the uncertainty sampling method to deep neural networks, e.g., CNN and Transformer, using estimated uncertainty from the models' predicted class posterior probabilities [28, 149]. However, as reported by Guo et al. [74], there is a mismatch between the probability associated with the predicted class label and the ground truth correctness likelihood in modern neural networks, also called "confidence miscalibration". As a result, the predicted class probability may not be an effective indicator of model confidence/certainty.

Different from studies that rely on hand-designed heuristics, *learnable AL* reforms informativeness evaluation involved in query strategies into a learnable component. Yoo and Kweon [182] introduced a task-agnostic approach that attaches a loss prediction module to a DNN to compute the uncertainty of the examined samples. The loss prediction module makes predictions on the losses of the target model and can be jointly learned with the target model. Data instances with higher expected losses are seen as more informative to current models. It resembles the spirit of the expected model change method but reduces the computational cost for estimating future losses using a loss prediction module.

Deep Bayesian AL provides another promising solution for the uncertainty estimation problem [140]. Unlike classical learning, which produces a set of deterministic parameters, in the Bayesian framework, the learners infer a posterior distribution over model parameters after observing the data. Therefore, Bayesian models can provide a probability distribution over predictions rather than point estimates, which possess uncertainty information that can be used with existing acquisition functions. Gal et al. [64] conjectured an AL framework for high-dimensional image data by using uncertainty information possessed in Bayesian Convolutional Neural Network (BCNN). It uses the estimated weight distribution of BCNN to approximate the intractable data acquisition functions defined in the AL framework.

Another important work in DeepAL is *core-set selection* that has been applied to CNN by Sener and Savarese [150]. This approach attempts to choose a subset of labeled data that yields comparable results to the entire dataset when used for model training.

5.1.3 Feedback Strategies

Feedback strategies, also called model update strategies, are methods that incorporate knowledge embedded in labels provided by human experts into the target model. While query strategies of AL focus on improving the informativeness and representativeness of selected instances, feedback strategies aim to maximize the benefits of interactions with annotators. When combining AL with supervised learning models, updating target models is straightforward, i.e., retraining or fine-tuning the models with newly labeled data. Yet, unsupervised learning methods are preferred in some fields, such as Key Performance Indicator (KPI) anomaly detection, since data labeling is extremely time- and resource-consuming and error-prone [19]. However, unsupervised learning methods can not directly exploit the label information and thus require additional feedback strategies. The success of AL combined with unsupervised learning methods requires careful design of feedback strategies.

An effective feedback strategy involves adjusting the optimization objectives of unsupervised learning algorithms to accommodate labeled data [76]. This approach is particularly widespread in anomaly detection [76, 41, 42, 115, 176, 40, 15, 174], where unsupervised learning techniques play a dominant role. Modifying the target model’s loss function (or learning objective) equips the models with a feedback module that measures the deviation of predicted labels to the true labels from annotators. For example, Wang et al. [174] proposed three feedback strategies, i.e., pseudo-labeling-based metric learning, denominator penalty, and negative penalty, which turned an unsupervised VAE into a semi-supervised method that can leverage labeling information in the AL setting.

5.2 Evaluation Metrics for AL Methods in Classification Problems

The evaluation of AL methods is heavily dependent on the tasks at hand and the specific learning models being used. In the case of assessing data quality, a common approach is to develop classifiers that categorize data instances as either “good” or “bad”, or across multiple quality levels. However, **data imbalance** poses a significant challenge for these classifiers, as incorrect data points are often rare and unexpected. This section offers an overview of evaluation metrics for AL classification methods that address data quality issue detection, with a particular focus on those suitable for imbalanced data. Table 10 lists the metrics discussed in this section.

Table 10: Common performance evaluation metrics for AL classification methods

Metrics	Characteristics
Precision, Recall, F1-score	Prevalent in classification problems
AUC	More sensitive to false-positives for heavily imbalanced dataset
PRBEP	Sometimes interchangeable with AUC
AUPRC	More discriminative than AUC
MCC	Less influenced by imbalanced test sets and suitable for multi-class classification
Kappa	Only valid for imbalanced data set
G-mean	Decreasing sharply when the performance of the classifier on the minority is much lower than the majority
Progress-curve [167]	In conjunction with other metrics to compare different query strategies using an equal number of query instances

Precision, Recall and *F1-score* are commonly used performance indicators in many tasks exploiting AL methods [142, 179, 191]. The recall represents the ratio of correctly identified instances with quality issues to all erroneous samples present in the dataset. Precision, on the other hand, indicates the proportion of data points that the model classifies as dirty data while being actually correct. The F1-score, serving as a compromise between precision and recall, is calculated as the geometric mean of the two metrics. *F1-Macro* and *F1-Micro* are used as performance indicators for multi-class data quality classification problems. *Accuracy* measurement is not recommended as performance metrics in this manner due to the misleading results on unbalanced datasets [68].

Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (ROC) curve represents the true positive rate against the false positive rate at different classification thresholds. *Area Under The ROC Curve (AUC)* provides an overall measure of a classifier’s performance, with larger values indicating better performance. Empirically, an AUC value greater than 0.7 indicates good model performance, while values between 0.6 and 0.7 are considered fair, and values below 0.6 suggest poor performance. The AUC metric is widely used in active learning-based anomaly detection [1, 38]. Similarly, *Area Under Precision-recall Curve (AUPRC)* (also known as PRAUC) quantifies classifier performance in terms of precision and recall. A perfect classifier achieves an AUPRC value of 1, indicating 100% precision and 100% recall simultaneously. *Precision-recall Break Even Point (PRBEP)* denotes the point where the precision-recall curve intersects the bisecting line, representing the accuracy of the positive class at the threshold where precision equals recall. There are inherent differences between AUC and AUPRC. In anomaly detection tasks with heavily imbalanced class distributions, the AUC metric is less sensitive to false positives than the AUPRC metric [102]. Previous studies [43, 144] demonstrate that the AUPRC score is more discriminative than the AUC score, and the model sensitivity can be evaluated by observing AUPRC [129].

Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) is another informative metric for evaluating a confusion matrix, which is less influenced by imbalanced test sets [36]. It remains applicable even if the classes differ significantly in size. MCC considers mutual accuracies and error rates for both classes, encompassing all confusion matrix values. Its range lies between -1 and $+1$, where a coefficient of $+1$ indicates a perfect prediction, 0 represents an average random

allocation, and -1 signifies the worst prediction. Furthermore, MCC can be generalized to multi-class problems [44, 122].

Cohen’s Kappa (Kappa) [170] receives more attention in the field of active anomaly detection, [178, 17, 125] and serves as a robust metric for imbalanced class problems. Kappa is defined as follows:

$$\kappa = P_0 - P_1 / (1 - P_1),$$

where P_0 represents the relative observed agreement among classifiers, and P_1 is the probability that the agreement is due to chance. Kappa achieves a value of 1 for perfect agreement with the ground truth and 0 when similar to a random prediction. However, it is more attainable to achieve a high value when the target class distribution is balanced, making this indicator valid primarily for imbalanced data.

G-mean is also a common metric for imbalanced data classification, defined as

$$g = \sqrt{\text{sensitivity} * \text{specificity}},$$

where sensitivity is the accuracy on the positive instances and specificity is the accuracy on the negative instances. G-mean measures the avoidance of overfitting to the negative class and the extent to which the positive class is marginalized. When the classifier’s performance on the minority class is significantly lower than the majority, G-mean declines sharply, indicating poor classifier performance. G-mean has been employed for assessing active learning classifiers over imbalanced datasets [54, 53, 180].

The *progress-curve* [167] is adapted from *learning curve*, a widely used tool in ML to evaluate a model’s performance when more training data is added. When applied to AL, it compares the effectiveness of different AL query strategies and learning models given the same amount of query instances, where the x-axis represents either the iteration number or the percentage of annotated observations and the y-axis measures a classification quality metrics, such as the true-positive rate. It is also applicable to multi-class classification problems combined with performance evaluation metrics like MCC or Kappa.

For an accurate and comprehensive performance assessment, it is recommended to utilize a combination of suitable metrics based on the specific conditions and to evaluate algorithms and query strategies from various perspectives. Robust metrics and the learning curve are particularly valuable in this regard, as they enable a more comprehensive and justified evaluation of efficiency.

6 Active Learning for Data Quality Control on Anomaly Detection

Due to its wide-ranging and application-specific nature, DQC encompasses numerous related studies that cannot be fully explored in a single article. Therefore, we will focus on the **anomaly detection** task, a common component of the DQC process, to illustrate how the AL paradigm can be adapted for DQC. Specifically, we will examine two DQC settings: *NRT-* and *delay-* mode. In the NRT mode, data quality assessment must be performed shortly after a data point arrives, while in the delay mode, data is gathered into a “pool” before being examined.

6.1 Pool-based AL for Delay-mode DQC

The delay-mode DQC is well-suited with the pool-based AL paradigm, as the system can accumulate data until it gains access to the entire dataset. Figure 4 depicts such a system. The system’s goal is to identify all anomalous data points in a dataset D , which is divided into an unlabeled set U and a labeled set L . An anomaly detector computes an anomaly score s for each sample from U and selects samples I to be reviewed by a domain expert based on its query strategy. The expert provides labels for these samples, which are then added to the labeled set L . Various query strategies, such as uncertainty sampling, margin sampling, or diversity sampling, are used to select the most valuable instances for labeling. These strategies identify data points that are challenging for the current DQC system to classify accurately or are likely to have a higher impact on data quality. This section reviews related studies applying pool-based AL techniques with different learning models, grouped into supervised and unsupervised learning methods.

6.1.1 Supervised Learning Methods

Supervised learning models, such as LR, kNN, and SVM, can be easily combined with AL since they can directly use the labels provided by human annotators. After receiving newly labeled data, updating models is usually done by re-training the models using all available labeled data. Table 11 lists studies employing supervised learners with various AL query strategies.

Russo et al. [142] applied AL to supervised ML methods to reduce the time and costs in automated anomaly detection of environmental monitoring data. Experimental results reported higher effectiveness of uncertainty sampling strategy

Figure 4: A delay-mode DQC system using pool-based AL methods

Table 11: Pool-based AL methods for delay-mode DQC with supervised learning models

Method	Query strategy	Learning models	Characteristics
Russo et al. [142]	Uncertainty sampling	NB; LR; kNN; RF; ANN	More effective than random sampling and complete labeling
Ziai [191]	Entropy-based sampling; Most anomalous	LR; RF	Entropy-based sampling is more efficient than most anomalous
Almgren and Jonsson [6]	Closest-to-decision-boundary sampling; Balanced sampling	SVM	The effectiveness of AL depends on the pool size and the problems' complexity
PMADS [129]	ADAL	SVM; LR; DT, RF; GBDT	ADAL is more time effective
GPSvas [104]	QBC	Linear-chain CRF	QBC can potentially improve performance of individual models
Chamborfort et al. [33]	Local risk-based method	kNN	Suitable for local classifiers

than random sampling and complete labeling, regardless of the ML classification algorithms used, including NB, LR, kNN, RF, Artificial Neural Network (ANN). Compared to random sampling, the uncertainty sampling method tends to select anomalies for label acquisition, which is more effective for model training in the context of anomaly detection. Performance evaluation with respect to F1-score showed that the RF, kNN, and ANN models achieved considerably higher performance compared to LR and NB models.

Ziai [191] compared entropy-based sampling with random sampling on a multivariate static dataset with LR and RF learners. Experiments showed that the entropy sampler with an RF learner achieved excellent detection accuracy within 5 queries but could not guarantee the optimal sequence of instances. They also explored the most anomalous query strategy using iForest. However, it turned out to be less effective than the entropy-based strategy.

Almgren and Jonsson [6] employed a closest-to-decision-boundary query strategy with an SVM classifier to separate innocuous data from attacks in the context of intrusion detection. They assume that the points closest to the SVM hyperplane are the ones of which the classifier is the most uncertain. They also investigated a balanced query strategy that forces an equal number of positive and negative examples. They found that the effectiveness of AL depends on both the pool size and the complexity of the problem. The larger the pool of unlabeled data, the more savings by using AL. In some circumstances, the reduction of labeled data can be as much as 80 times. However, for problems where

the final SVM has many support vectors (indirectly implying the problem to be more complex), results showed less gain as compared with a random learner.

Pan et al. [129] devised an ADAL query strategy that randomly selects a subset from the top- k samples ranked by an unsupervised anomaly detector. It was applied to microwave link anomaly detection in cellular data networks. The query strategy works together with supervised classifiers, such as LR, SVM, DT, Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT), and RF. ADAL is far more computationally effective than other AL query strategies, such as uncertainty sampling and QBC sampling, while keeping comparable Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (PRAUC). They also pointed out that time efficiency requires more concern in real applications and that AL can lose its advantage if it takes too long to receive the labeling result of a query.

Liao et al. [104] introduced the GPS Visual Analytics System (GPSvas) to detect anomalies in GPS data. The linear-chain Conditional Random Field (CRF) model is used to extract features from GPS streaming data and the QBC strategy is to improve the robustness of anomaly detection. The committee, composed of five separate CRF models initially trained using different sets of training sequences, selects the instance by the member's highest prediction confidence. For each single model, the instance sampling criteria are three-fold: uncertainty, representativeness, and diversity. The uncertainty-based approach is implemented as least-confidence sampling, where the model confidence is measured by the conditional probability of label y of \mathbf{x} $P(y|\mathbf{x})$. They also introduced a representativeness measurement, which yields a high value for samples that are not similar to any other sequence in the candidate set. To ensure diversity, they remove redundant items with respect to data items already in the training set from the previous iteration. They confirmed that the QBC strategy improved prediction accuracy and could potentially achieve performance better than any of the individual models.

Chamborfort et al. [33] applied AL to noise detection on seismic times series data. They proposed a local risk-based query strategy, which selects instances that maximize the local risk function. This method works under the assumption that adding a point to the training dataset would not make a drastic change in the local risk function, and is thus suitable for local classifiers, such as kNN or RF, and is expected to perform badly with non-local classifiers, such as LR. The Nadaraya-Watson (also called local-constant) estimator is exploited to assess the local risk function. Taking into account the human factors, they opted for a batch-mode approach, where geophysics experts are asked to annotate 20 seismic images at once. Evaluated on the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (WBC) dataset, their method achieved the best performance and was significantly better than the passive and uncertain strategies.

6.1.2 Unsupervised Learning Methods

Applying AL to supervised learning models may seem simple, but two issues are commonly encountered. The first challenge is the dependence on a substantial amount of labeled data for effective performance. In the context of AL, this can lead to the cold-start problem or failure when the annotation budget is strictly constrained. The second concern is the underutilization of unlabeled data, causing a significant wastage of available resources. To overcome this, a potential solution involves leveraging unsupervised models to make the most of the abundant unlabeled data. Relevant studies are summarized in Table 12.

Görnitz et al. [76] proposed SSAD, a mathematical sound semi-supervised anomaly detection method built upon an unsupervised learning paradigm. By introducing labeled signals into the optimization objectives, it incorporates labeled data into the unsupervised learning algorithm Support Vector Data Description (SVDD). A combination of margin strategy and cluster strategy is utilized to acquire instances close to the hypersphere's boundary and lie in potentially anomalous clusters concerning the k -nearest neighbor graph. SSAD significantly improves prediction accuracy by effectively exploiting the limited amount of labeled data. It only needs 3% of the data to attain a good separation, while random sampling needs 25%.

Das et al. [41] introduced LODA-AAD, which applies active learning to the LODA [134] algorithm ensemble approach to anomaly detection. In LODA-AAD, data instances are internally ranked based on their anomaly scores computed by the LODA algorithm. The objective is to have true anomalies ranked within the top- τ quantile. The loss function penalizes rankings that violate this rule. To obtain labeled instances, analysts annotate top-ranked unlabeled examples. With each labeled instance, ensemble members' weights are adjusted to push false positives down in the internal ranking model while elevating true anomalies. Later, the authors extended their work to the iForest model to detect anomalies using expert feedback, resulting in IF-AAD [42]. IF-AAD treats the regions defined by the nodes of isolation trees as components of an ensemble and adjusts their weights based on the feedback from analysts. In many cases, IF-AAD outperforms both the iForest baseline method and LODA-AAD in discovering more anomalies over time.

Another related study is ALIF [115], which actively queries novel instances and modifies the iForest to include feedback from experts. However, the updating of trees is different from IF-AAD [42]. Every time a novel point is queried,

Table 12: Pool-based AL methods for delay-mode DQC with unsupervised learning models

Method	Query strategy	Feedback strategy	Learning model	Characteristics
SSAD [76]	Margin+cluster	Modification to optimization objectives	SVDD	Rephrasing unsupervised learning problem to a semi-supervised task
LODA-AAD [41]	Most anomalous	Re-weighting ensemble members [21]	LODA [134]	Casting anomaly detection problem as a ranking problem
IF-AAD [42]	Most anomalous	Re-weighting nodes within the trees of a forest [21]	iForest	Similar to LODA-AAD [41]
ALIF [115]	Maximum uncertainty; Most anomalous	Piece-wise linear depth and the logarithmic depth	iForest	Specifically designed for iForest
GLAD [40]	Most anomalous	Updating the weights of the FSSN	Generic ensembles	Applicable to generic ensemble anomaly detection methods
Hamza Bodor et al. [19]	TA; CTDB; TA+CTDB	Tree weights update [176]; Offset update	iForest	Extensive experiments on different combinations of methods
iRRCF-Active [176]	Most anomalous	Re-weighting trees based on labels	RRCF [73]	Converting feedback to model optimization
ALOD, ALOD-RE [15]	70% from AL query strategies, 30% outlier detectors	Re-training the model	Not specified	AL and learning models are separated
Active-MTSAD [174]	Ensemble query strategy	Pseudo-Labeling-based Metric Learning, denominator penalty and negative penalty	LSTM-based VAE	Customized VAE training process
RLAD [179]	Margin sampling on Q-value	Label propagation	LSTM-based RL agent	Combining RL and AL

each iTree exclusively updates the leaf containing the queried point, leaving the rest unchanged. Its depth (computed by the iForest) is forgotten and substituted with piece-wise linear depth or the logarithmic depth, depending on the *color* of the leaf under investigation. The query strategies applied are maximum uncertainty and most anomalous.

Building upon the concept of dynamic ensemble weighting, Das et al. expanded their research to generic ensembles and introduced GLocalized Anomaly Detection (GLAD) [40]. GLAD employs an ensemble of anomaly detectors to assign anomaly scores to instances. Additionally, each detector is associated with a relevance score for each instance, predicted by a neural network called Feature Space Suppression Network (FSSN). Upon receiving label feedback from analysts, the FSSN adjusts its weights to suppress all erroneous detectors. However, the anomaly detectors themselves are not directly updated. Instead, their weights in the FSSN (referred to as the relevance to a particular instance) are modified to ensure that true anomalies are consistently ranked at the top.

Hamza Bodor et al. [19] also combined the iForest model and AL. They exploited the Top Anomalous Selection (TA), Close to Decision Boundary Selection (CTDB), and TA+CTDB query strategy (half of the budget for instances with the highest anomaly scores and another half for instances closest to the decision boundary). They evaluated the tree weights update [176] and the offset update methods for model updating. The offset update approach adopts rule-based thresholding to learn the offset value based on the feedback for queried points, which demonstrated superior performance compared to a linear SVM based on their experiments. They also indicated that TA outperformed random selection, CTDB, and TA+CTDB methods. Moreover, when compared to the baseline iForest model, the proposed AL pipeline achieved an impressive 56.51% performance improvement using just 1% of the query budget. Additionally, it required a smaller query budget to achieve the best performance compared to GLAD [40].

Wang et al. [176] introduced iRRCF-Active for KPI anomaly detection. Their approach involved enhancing the original Robust Random Cut Forest (RRCF) model’s capacity and detection speed by using an improved version called

iRRCF. A simple active learning query strategy was integrated with the iRRCF anomaly detector to leverage expert knowledge. Specifically, the top 30 instances with the highest anomaly scores assigned by iRRCF were recommended for labeling. Regarding model updating, iRRCF-Active evaluates which trees are more reliable in terms of classification and accordingly gives higher weights to these trees.

Mayukh Bhattacharjee et al. [15] explicitly discussed the data imbalance problem in AL-based classification tasks. They proposed a novel approach called Active Learning with Outlier Detection (ALOD) that combines outlier detection techniques with AL to select the most appropriate instances from the unlabeled dataset. The ALOD algorithm operates in a batch-mode setting, where 70% of the batch samples are chosen using AL query strategies, and the remaining 30% samples are selected through outlier detectors. To address the data imbalance problem further, they introduced a second algorithm called ALOD-RE, which incorporates resampling methods such as SMOTE, ADASYN, or Random Oversampling to create a more balanced training set. For instance acquisition, they leveraged uncertainty sampling and QBC. Although they claimed the methods to be semi-supervised, the ALOD and ALOD-RE techniques essentially combine instances selected separately by supervised learning models and unsupervised learning models. There is no modification made to the loss functions of unsupervised learning models to incorporate expert feedback, i.e., data labels.

Unlike the above methods that combine AL with traditional ML models, Active-MTSAD [174] applies AL to deep learning models via a sophisticated semi-supervised approach to include feedback directly to the unsupervised learning model, named MTSAD. The anomaly detector MTSAD is a VAE with LSTM networks as encoder and decoder. The Active-MTSAD method adopts an ensemble query strategy composed of top- k sampling, uncertainty sampling, and interval random sampling, which has been demonstrated to be more effective than individual query strategies. They proposed three feedback strategies to fully use labeled samples: *Pseudo-Labeling-based Metric Learning*, *Denominator Penalty*, and *Negative Penalty*, to explicitly utilize label information. In the first feedback strategy, a metric loss is added to the original loss of MTSAD to minimize feature distances from the same class on the latent space while maximizing these from different classes. The last two feedback strategies introduce penalty terms for labeled anomalous samples. The denominator penalty strategy utilizes the inverse of the reconstruction loss, whereas the negative penalty uses the negative of the reconstruction loss. Both are multiplied by a hyperparameter to control the balance between unlabeled and labeled samples.

Wu et al. [179] introduced a novel combination of deep RL for anomaly detection with AL. Their proposed model, RLAD, does not rely on assumptions about the underlying mechanism generating the observation sequence. Instead, it continuously adapts the detection model based on experience with anomalous patterns. The anomaly detection problem is formulated as a Markov decision process and solved using the Deep Q Network (DQN) method. An RL agent, equipped with a LSTM neural network as its brain, generates Q-values for states and actions. In this context, instances are treated as states, and the actions represent the RL agent’s predictions regarding whether they are anomalies. To select instances for expert inspection, a margin sampling method is employed on the Q-values, which reflect the potential rewards the RL agent could obtain. The Label propagation method is also used to generate pseudo-labels for unlabeled data using labeled instances. Evaluated on two time-series datasets, RLAD outperforms all existing unsupervised techniques. Moreover, when provided with the same number of labels, RLAD achieves better performance than the semi-supervised approach Deep-SAD [131].

One significant advantage of employing supervised learning techniques within AL is that it does not necessitate the design of sophisticated feedback strategies. When dealing with rapid learning models like SVM, LR, and ANN, it is common practice to re-train these learners. Consequently, the primary focus in these approaches typically revolves around the query strategy, specifically how to assess the informativeness of each instance based on the current state of the models. However, this approach does not apply to unsupervised learning methods as they intrinsically do not learn from label signals. Therefore, adjustments must be made either to the structure of these models or to their learning process to enable them to optimize with data labels. In such cases, they technically transform into semi-supervised learning models. From another point of view, unsupervised learning models face fewer challenges related to cold-start problems since they can be initialized using solely unlabeled data. In contrast, supervised learning models require at least a small set of labeled samples to initiate the learning process.

6.2 Stream-based AL for NRT-mode DQC

A real-time or near-real-time DQC system has stringent timeliness requirements compared to a delay-mode system. Its primary objective is to rapidly assess the quality of data instances within a continuous data stream. This presents a significant challenge known as **concept drift** [193], where the statistical properties of the data change over time, gradually or instantly invalidating the learning models [112]. It commonly occurs in non-stationary data environments, particularly in online learning systems [86]. Stream-based AL approaches can be a promising solution for this challenge. The visual representation in Figure 5 illustrates a NRT-mode DQC system employing stream-based AL methods. In

this system, a data stream arrives sequentially as $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T\}$, and it must decide whether to query its label for the current sample x_t . An anomaly detector predicts potential outliers and selects specific samples according to the query strategy to be labeled by annotators. These labeled samples are then incorporated into the anomaly detector using feedback strategies, enhancing its ability to predict anomalies in the given data block. This section presents a review of the relevant literature on this subject.

Figure 5: A NRT-mode DQC system using stream-based AL methods

6.2.1 Supervised Learning Models

Different from pool-based AL methods, stream-based AL (or online AL) approaches have to decide, for the current unlabeled datum, whether to query its label or not [37]. This implies two matters: 1) query strategy takes effect solely on the current fragment of data; neither past nor future data can be queried; 2) past predictions for unlabeled data can't be modified along with the update of models upon receiving new labeled data. Related studies are summarized in Table 13.

Loy et al. [111] applied stream-based AL combined with Bayesian classifiers for online unusual event detection. They presented an adaptive multi-criteria query approach to select instances that are likely to be most influential on the current model. Specifically, a *minimum likelihood* and a *modified QBC* algorithms are dynamically re-weighted based on the change in distribution modeled by a naive Bayes classifier before and after it is updated using a newly queried sample. Experiments on the MIT traffic video dataset [175] suggested a superior performance of the proposed approach compared to existing single-criterion and multi-criteria query strategies.

Wei et al. [37] proposed a Bayesian framework for unbiased stream-based AL in binary classification problems. They implemented the framework in a simplified setting in which the classifiers are linear models governed by weights following a multi-variate Gaussian distribution. They adopted a weighted likelihood bootstrap sampling method for selecting instances for labeling. The biases in data selection are addressed by assigning importance weights to instances and incorporating them into the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) process. To combat the dynamics in data distribution, they introduced a memory loss factor on the current model to decrease the influence of out-of-date samples.

Zhao and Hoi [187] proposed CSOAL, a cost-sensitive online AL method, to tackle malicious Uniform Resource Locator (URL) detection problems. Considering the data imbalance challenge in real-world applications, they introduced

Table 13: Stream-based AL methods for NRT-mode DQC with supervised learning models

Method	Query strategy	Feedback strategy	Learning model	Characteristics
Loy et al. [111]	Adaptive multi-criteria query	Update classifier with new queried samples	Bayesian classifier	Multi-criteria query strategy outperforms single-criterion ones
Wei et al. [37]	Weighted likelihood bootstrap sampling	SGD with importance weights and memory loss factor	Bayesian classifier	Considering unbiasedness property in instance selection
CSOAL [187]	Bernoulli random sampling with predicted probability	Cost-sensitive optimization objectives	Linear classifier	Significantly reducing the amount of labeled data (0.5% or less).
Zhang et al. [186]	Asymmetric query model	Perceptron update	Linear classifier	Effective in highly class-imbalanced datasets
Ghassemi et al. [69]	Online T-K strategy	Differentially private SGD	Batch SVM	Privacy-preserving online AL

two cost-sensitive measures as new performance metrics for learning algorithms, i.e., the weighted sum of sensitivity and the weighted cost. The proposed CSOAL algorithm adopts a linear classifier and decides if the class label should be queried according to a Bernoulli random variable where the probability is determined by the classifier prediction and controlled by a sampling factor parameter. An empirical study illustrated that CSOAL attained the comparable (or even better) SOTA predictive performance of a cost-sensitive online learner by querying a significantly small amount of labeled data (0.5% or less).

Another study related to data imbalance in online AL is conducted by Zhang et al. [186]. They proposed an asymmetric query model to address the imbalanced problem between positive and negative examples. A theoretical analysis of the weighted mistake bound is provided, and the experimental results compared with four baseline sampling strategies showed its effectiveness in highly class-imbalanced datasets.

Unlike the above methods that strive to select the most informative instances for model optimization, Ghassemi et al. [69] concentrated on employing differentially private techniques to address privacy concerns during the training of an anomaly detection SVM classifier. They proposed an *online T-K query* strategy to detect anomalies in stream-based data and incorporated two randomized selections to ensure privacy. Additionally, to maintain privacy during the update steps, they utilized a differentially private SGD method with two update strategies: the fixed-length selection window (FLSW) policy and the fixed-length mini-batch (FLMB) policy. The experimental results showed that the proposed algorithms have acceptable generalization performance while preserving the differential privacy of user data.

The studies reviewed in this context tackle various challenges related to stream-based AL, including dynamic environments [111], imbalanced data [37, 187, 186], and privacy concerns [69]. Much of the literature is supported by rigorous theoretical analyses. However, these methods are predominantly implemented with simple learning models like linear classifiers, SVM, and naive Bayesian classifiers. There is still a need for further endeavors to develop and validate online AL approaches applied to more complex learning models, such as CNN, LSTM, Transformers, etc.

6.2.2 Unsupervised Learning Models

Compared to supervised learning models in stream-based AL, there are limited studies related to unsupervised learning models. Table 14 summarizes studies utilizing unsupervised learning methods.

Christopher Nixon et al. [125] proposed SALAD, which aims to provide a low-cost online anomaly detection solution using Autoencoder (AE). The anomalies are detected using AE’s reconstruction error compared with a dynamic threshold determined by the Adaptive Anomaly Threshold method [66]. To deal with concept drift, they employed the Drift Detection Method (DDM) [65] for change detection and two anomaly detectors for change adaption. They paired the main anomaly detector AE with a recent anomaly detector AE_L that is trained with the most recent examples. If the warning signal is triggered, AE_L will start training and replace AE when there is a change signal. They introduced a *split strategy* that combines the random and variable uncertainty (uncertainty with varied confidence) strategies for deciding whether to query an instance. It reported the best results on KDD Cup 1999 and UNSW-NB15 [120] data set compared to random, uncertainty, and variable uncertainty strategies. They also showed that the AE method within the proposed Active Stream Framework significantly reduced the labeling cost to a budget of 20%.

Table 14: Stream-based AL methods for NRT-mode DQC with unsupervised learning models

Method	Query strategy	Feedback strategy	Learning model	Characteristics
SALAD [125]	Split strategy (random+variable uncertainty)	Incremental learning with DDM [65]	AE	Considering concept drift in streaming data; Uncertainty strategy applied to AE

Stream-based AL methods require making real-time decisions to label incoming data points, making them more intricate and demanding than pool-based AL methods. The stream setting of AL approaches affects not only the query strategy (as the query strategy can not traverse the entire dataset to select the most informative instances) but also the learning models and the feedback strategy. Stream-based AL is often built upon streaming learning (or online learning) [98], where the learners are assumed to have limited access to the labeled data and thus models are trained continuously as new data becomes available. Under this assumption, the feedback strategy for these learners is usually in an incremental manner, whereas in the pool-based AL, the models can be simply re-trained when new labeled instances become available. Therefore, we recommend investigating effective DQC methods using stream learning before transforming them into an AL approach. Additionally, the occurrence of concept drift poses a significant obstacle to the effectiveness of stream-based AL approaches as real-world streaming data is inherently non-stationary. While some research has been dedicated to addressing this issue [125], it remains relatively less explored than pool-based AL paradigms. We suggest researchers first examine the existence of concept drift in target data, and utilize concept drift detection and adaption mechanisms to improve the robustness of AL methods if necessary.

6.3 Considerations in Real Applications

To successfully incorporate AL into DQC systems, it is essential to carefully choose suitable learning models, query strategies, and feedback strategies that align with the specific needs of the DQC system. The system’s performance is typically evaluated based on two crucial dimensions: **accuracy** and **latency**. While accuracy traditionally takes center stage in laboratory research, it’s important to consider latency from a system-level perspective, as it significantly influences the overall usability of the real applications [129]. We illustrate the interplay between AL components and the demands of a DQC system in Figure 6, which serves as a reference for designing real-world AL-based DQC applications.

Figure 6: Relations between AL components and system performance in real applications

Assuming that the labels from human annotators represent the ground truth, the accuracy of the system depends primarily on the quality assessors (the learning models using AL’s term), query strategy, and feedback strategy of AL methods, and the number of labeled samples constrained by the annotation budget. Latency is influenced by not only the underlying algorithms but also human annotators. We emphasize the often overlooked significance of human factors when designing a human-involved DQC system. Specifically, the experts’ annotation velocity, i.e., how long it takes to label one observation, can emerge as a potential bottleneck in certain scenarios. The main cause of this

issue is the sequential nature of operations within one AL cycle. The learning model must await human input before commencing the next inference and sample selection round. While this might not be a problem if labeling a data instance takes negligible time, significant delays can occur if the labeling process consumes considerably more time than the inference and data acquisition processes. On the other hand, human experts may prefer to deliver feedback on multiple instances at once, which necessitates a batch-mode AL setting [33]. Giving careful consideration to and effectively dealing with these human factors during the development of AL-based DQC methods is crucial to maximizing the overall system’s efficiency.

In practical scenarios where annotating an instance is particularly challenging or costly, such as annotating medical images for rare diseases or legal documents for potential risks, we suggest considering unsupervised learning methods that leverage highly effective labeled signals [174] or pre-trained models trained on abundant labeled data from other sources, which can then be fine-tuned with a small number of labeled instances from the target domain [157]. To reduce latency in DQC systems, the primary focus should be on identifying and enhancing the most time-consuming components. If the bottleneck lies in the learning model update process, it is advisable to keep the learning models lightweight, for example, by employing DT, SVM, or RF, to enable fast updates. Conversely, if annotating a single instance is considerably slower than model updating, consider employing batch-mode AL with multiple annotators working in parallel. Furthermore, if selecting the best instances is time-consuming due to an exceptionally large data pool, an exploration-exploitation strategy can be adopted for the query strategy.

Table 15: Summary of characteristics of reviewed studies. ✓ stands for included, and × for NOT included.

Characteristic	Delay-mode DQC		NRT-mode DQC	
	Supervised	Unsupervised	Supervised	Unsupervised
Pool-based AL	✓	✓	×	×
Stream-based AL	×	×	✓	✓
Single-mode sampling	✓	✓	×	×
Batch-mode sampling	✓	✓	×	×
RL-based sampling	×	✓	✓	×
Stationary stream sampling	×	×	✓	×
Shifting stream sampling	×	×	✓	✓
Retraining models	✓	✓	×	×
Ad-hoc feedback strategy	×	✓	✓	✓
Data imbalance	×	✓	×	✓

To summarize this section, we use anomaly detection as an exemplar to illustrate the adoption of AL in DQC under two settings: delay-mode DQC and NRT-mode DQC. Table 15 provides an overview of the methods and their characteristics reviewed in this section. We organize the reviewed methods from the perspectives of AL scenarios, query strategy types, feedback strategy types and additional considerations such as data imbalance.

7 Challenges and Opportunities

Despite the promising prospect of this field, many open questions still exist [152, 172, 27]. We outline the challenges and potential opportunities related to this field, highlighting the research directions that could benefit from further investigation and efforts.

7.1 Challenges in DQC Model Development

7.1.1 Anomalies or Errors

One constant discussion within the DQC community is about anomalies and errors. Anomalies/outliers usually deviate too much from normal patterns and thus appear to be data errors. In many cases, they are indeed errors, which are caused by sensor malfunctions or data transmission faults. Recognizing and mitigating these errors are paramount tasks of DQC. For example, Eskin [55] has applied anomaly detection to identify errors from a marked corpus based on the assumption that anomalous elements are typically marking errors. However, observatory data sometimes contain data anomalies by nature, caused by environmental changes and novel events. These anomalies are not errors, but rather a representation of an unusual phenomenon. Some studies, e.g., novelty detection [135], rely on the existence of these “abnormal” data to discover interesting and valuable knowledge. On the other hand, errors may not seem like

anomalies and thus require data analysts’ expertise to distinguish them from the normal data distribution. Therefore, it is of great importance to clarify the concepts of anomalies and errors before designing the learning models.

7.1.2 Coexisting Data Quality Issues

Datasets often encompass multiple quality issues, such as anomalies, missing values, duplicates, and errors. Consequently, it is necessary to break down the problem and assign priorities to address each quality issue effectively. Researchers have explored methods capable of addressing multiple data quality issues simultaneously. For instance, Halder et al. [78] introduced a fuzzy adaptive imputation technique that not only handles missing data but also addresses class imbalance. Data anomaly and data imbalance problems also often coincide.

7.2 Challenges in Applying AL Methods

7.2.1 Batch-mode AL

Batch-mode AL is the foundation of DeepAL [140] as the one-by-one query method is inefficient for optimizing DL models, which leads to frequent model training but trivial data change. In addition, it does not fit well with many practical DQC systems due to data analysts’ preference to annotate multiple samples at once. However, batch-mode AL poses great challenges in query strategy design. AL often relies on estimating the uncertainty of the model’s predictions. In batch-mode AL, accurately estimating the uncertainty across a batch of instances can be challenging. Moreover, determining the appropriate batch size is not always straightforward. A larger batch size can lead to greater computational demands and labeling costs, while a smaller batch size might not fully exploit the benefits of batch learning.

7.2.2 Incremental Learning

Updating the model with newly labeled samples is an integral part of the iterative AL process. The efficiency of this updating process, in terms of both time and computational resources, can significantly impact the overall effectiveness of the AL approach. As we discussed in Section 5.1.3, one common approach for model updating involves retraining supervised learning models. However, this method faces challenges when applied to deep neural networks such as CNNs, RNNs, and Transformers, as training these models can be time-intensive. A promising direction of research in this regard is *incremental learning*, especially *domain-incremental learning* (different from task-incremental learning and class-incremental learning) [168]. Incremental learning is designed to acquire new knowledge from a continuously changing stream of data without completely forgetting previous knowledge (so-called catastrophic forgetting [61]), while domain-incremental learning specifically addresses issues that arise when the context or input distribution changes. They can be leveraged by AL methods to enable continuous model updates without training from scratch. It is intuitive to apply incremental learning to stream-based AL since they both deal with data streams. In contrast, for pool-based AL, applying incremental learning can be seen as simulating a dynamically evolving data stream as more data labels are gradually revealed. Shi et al. [157] introduced an incremental AL method for automatic atrial fibrillation detection, where the pre-trained model was fine-tuned continuously by the most informative samples in the candidate set in the incremental learning stage. Their work can be employed in pool-based AL scenarios provided that the pre-trained models have sufficient generalizability and previously labeled data throughout the AL process is fully accessible. Differently, in a more restricted setting, all the previous training data are not available at the current time, and only the model parameters of the previous stages are accessible. In this case, the catastrophic forgetting problem becomes one major challenge. Yang et al. [181] proposed an incremental adaptive deep model (IADM) to support deep models’ capacity scalability and sustainability over a drifting data stream. They developed an evolutive deep network using an attention mechanism that can automatically learn the optimal network depth in sequence. Meanwhile, they introduced weighted fisher regularization to overcome the catastrophic forgetting issue in sequence learning.

7.2.3 Domain Shift and Concept Drift

In the real world, data is often produced by multiple sensory equipment and/or in a streaming manner. It brings into focus two important challenges: *domain shift* and *concept drift*. Domain shift occurs when the statistical properties of the data change across different environments, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data from different patients. It becomes problematic if it happens between training and test data since the models’ performance relies on the assumption that the training and test data conform to the same distribution. In the case of DQC, the domain shift issue appears when attempting to apply data quality assessment models trained by data generated from some equipment to those from other equipment. To address this issue, various *domain adaptation* techniques have been developed, letting the model learn to generalize from a source domain to a target domain [58]. Domain adaptation

methods can be employed within an AL setting, where they assume that there is a large amount of labeled data from a source domain, a large amount of unlabeled data from a target domain, and a small budget for acquiring labels in the target domain [139].

Concept drift refers to the changes over time in the joint distribution between the input feature and the ground truth labels. This phenomenon is particularly common in data streams and has received significant attention in recent years. Lu et al. [112] provided a comprehensive review of related work, including concept drift detection, understanding, and adaptation. However, the application of AL in the context of concept drift remains relatively unexplored. Dealing with concept drift introduces additional complexities for AL. As highlighted by Žliobaitė et al. [192], “traditional active learning distorts the incoming data distribution expecting more effective learning, while active learning with data streams must preserve the incoming data distribution to the extent that changes could be detected as they happen”. Consequently, AL approaches must allocate a portion of the labeling budget, either explicitly or implicitly, to address concept drift. For instance, Zhang et al. [184] employed a dynamic classifier that is continuously created and replaced based on the current data block to capture the local concept, along with a stable classifier to monitor the long-term trends in the data stream. For every new dynamic classifier, a fixed portion of instances within the data block has to be labeled to train the new classifier.

7.3 Challenges in Building a Practical DQC System

Besides the challenges involved in developing DQC models and AL approaches, there are other problems involved in developing DQC systems in realistic environments, such that certain assumptions about data are breached and countermeasures are required.

7.3.1 Noisy Oracle

AL methods often make an unrealistic assumption that the oracle is consistently reliable, meaning that the labels provided by the oracle are always completely accurate. However, in real-world situations, this assumption can easily be violated because human experts often serve as oracles and can make mistakes and introduce errors to the labels [99]. To tackle this challenge, some AL approaches have been developed to explicitly model the behavior of human-like oracles. In a study by Du and Ling [46], they investigated how a human-like noisy oracle tends to provide incorrect answers based on two key assumptions. Firstly, they linked the likelihood of human oracles producing correct answers to their confidence in those answers. Secondly, they used the maximum posterior probability generated by the target model to estimate the confidence of the human oracle. Building on these assumptions, they devised a novel query strategy to select unlabeled examples that are less likely to be incorrectly labeled while still offering high informational value.

In a more general scenario, there may be multiple noisy oracles involved, such as in crowd-sourcing annotation where numerous annotators contribute annotations with varying levels of noise simultaneously. Chakraborty [31] proposed a framework for addressing the challenge of batch-mode AL when multiple imperfect labeling oracles are present. In this context, the oracles are also involved in a selection process based on the labeling cost and the error probability conditions.

7.3.2 Annotation Cost Calculation

In the majority of studies utilizing AL, it is typically assumed that the cost associated with annotating each data instance is uniform, and thus, the total cost is solely determined by the number of selected instances. However, this assumption doesn't hold true in real-world scenarios, where annotation costs can significantly differ based on factors such as the complexity of labeling and the efficiency of the annotation process. For instance, in the field of medicine, evaluating contentious medical images may demand more time and resources compared to routine ones, making them more “expensive” to label. Settles et al. [153] conducted an extensive empirical study into annotation costs across four practical domains involving text and image data. Their findings confirmed considerable variations in annotation costs among different instances. Additionally, they demonstrated that, even with limited training examples, it is possible to build predictive models for estimating annotation costs accurately. Based on the above observation, they proposed to train a cost model to predict annotation costs while simultaneously training the actual task-model. Their work outlined two important research directions, i.e., *annotation cost estimation*, which focuses on building models for predicting annotation costs, and *cost-sensitive AL*, which investigates AL methods that take into consideration the varying annotation costs. Haertel et al. [77] employed an hourly cost model to evaluate AL algorithms for POS annotation using the sentence length and the accuracy of the model. In a related study, Haertel et al. [77] employed an hourly cost model to assess AL algorithms for part-of-speech (POS) annotation. The cost model incorporated factors like sentence length and model accuracy.

8 Conclusion

Data Quality Control (DQC) is crucial for delivering high-quality and reliable data to downstream applications. In the Big Data era, manual DQC has become inefficient and error-prone. While fully automated DQC still faces great challenges, the human-in-the-loop DQC approaches can be promising alternatives. Active Learning (AL), a technique designed to minimize labeling costs, can be harnessed to alleviate the workload of data analysts involved in DQC. This survey is conducted to answer five key research questions concerning the application of AL in the context of DQC, as described in Section 3. To answer RQ1, we summarized seven common data quality issues in the ML area, from which we introduced the tackling methods for three data quality issues, i.e., data anomaly, data scarcity and data imbalance. To answer RQ2, we first introduced the core concepts involved in the AL field, including three scenarios and four components. Then we reviewed techniques developed in AL that are related to, or have the potential to be applied in, data quality issue detection. Additionally, we introduced evaluation metrics commonly used for AL methods. To answer RQ3 and RQ4, we provided two application scenarios of AL methods on the anomaly detection task for delay-mode DQC and NRT-mode DQC, respectively. Finally, we outlined the challenges and opportunities from three perspectives, including DQC model development, applying AL methods and building a practical DQC system, to answer RQ5.

In summary, AL emerges as a powerful tool for DQC, offering promising solutions to enhance the assessment of data quality through human expert involvement. AL’s application has been examined on specific DQC tasks, such as anomaly detection, and under varying contexts such as NRT-mode DQC. To facilitate the adoption of AL methods in real-world applications, it is valuable to explore the connections and hence coordinate among state-of-art DQC techniques, relevant AL methodologies, and realistic DQC environments.

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References

- [1] Naoki Abe, Bianca Zadrozny, and John Langford. 2006. Outlier detection by active learning. In *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*. 504–509.
- [2] Charu C Aggarwal. 2017. In Data Mining. In *Outlier analysis*. Springer.
- [3] Charu C Aggarwal, Xiangnan Kong, Quanquan Gu, Jiawei Han, and S Yu Philip. 2014. Active learning: A survey. In *Data classification*. Chapman and Hall/CRC, 599–634.
- [4] Hamed H Aghdam, Abel Gonzalez-Garcia, Joost van de Weijer, and Antonio M López. 2019. Active learning for deep detection neural networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 3672–3680.
- [5] Gabriel Aguiar, Bartosz Krawczyk, and Alberto Cano. 2023. A survey on learning from imbalanced data streams: taxonomy, challenges, empirical study, and reproducible experimental framework. *Machine Learning (2023)*, 1–79.
- [6] Magnus Almgren and Erland Jonsson. 2004. Using active learning in intrusion detection. In *Proceedings. 17th IEEE Computer Security Foundations Workshop, 2004*. IEEE, 88–98.
- [7] Laith Alzubaidi, Jinshuai Bai, Aiman Al-Sabaawi, Jose Santamaría, AS Albahri, Bashar Sami Nayyef Al-dabbagh, Mohammed A Fadhel, Mohamed Manoufali, Jinglan Zhang, Ali H Al-Timemy, et al. 2023. A survey on deep learning tools dealing with data scarcity: definitions, challenges, solutions, tips, and applications. *Journal of Big Data* 10, 1 (2023), 46.
- [8] Samaneh Aminikhanghahi and Diane J Cook. 2017. A survey of methods for time series change point detection. *Knowledge and information systems* 51, 2 (2017), 339–367.
- [9] Shin Ando and Chun Yuan Huang. 2017. Deep over-sampling framework for classifying imbalanced data. In *Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases: European Conference, ECML PKDD 2017, Skopje, Macedonia, September 18–22, 2017, Proceedings, Part I 10*. Springer, 770–785.
- [10] Dana Angluin. 1988. Queries and Concept Learning. *Machine learning* 2, 4 (1988), 319–.
- [11] Michele Banko and Eric Brill. 2001. Scaling to very very large corpora for natural language disambiguation. In *Proceedings of the 39th annual meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. 26–33.

- [12] Ms Aayushi Bansal, Dr Rewa Sharma, and Dr Mamta Kathuria. 2020. A Systematic Review on Data Scarcity Problem in Deep Learning: Solution and Applications. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* (2020).
- [13] Vic Barnett and Toby Lewis. 1984. Outliers in statistical data. *Wiley Series in Probability and Mathematical Statistics. Applied Probability and Statistics* (1984).
- [14] Eric B Baum and Kenneth Lang. 1992. Query learning can work poorly when a human oracle is used. In *International joint conference on neural networks*, Vol. 8. Beijing China, 8.
- [15] Mayukh Bhattacharjee, Hema Sri Kambhampati, Paula Branco, and Luis Torgo. 2021. Active Learning for Imbalanced Domains: the ALOD and ALOD-RE Algorithms. In *2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*. 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/DSAA53316.2021.9564145>
- [16] Ane Blázquez-García, Angel Conde, Usue Mori, and Jose A Lozano. 2021. A review on outlier/anomaly detection in time series data. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 54, 3 (2021), 1–33.
- [17] Michael Bloodgood and John Grothendieck. 2015. Analysis of stopping active learning based on stabilizing predictions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1504.06329* (2015).
- [18] Raymond Board and Leonard Pitt. 1989. Semi-Supervised Learning. *Machine learning* 4, 1 (1989), 41–.
- [19] Hamza Bodor, Thai V. Hoang, and Zonghua Zhang. 2022. Little Help Makes a Big Difference: Leveraging Active Learning to Improve Unsupervised Time Series Anomaly Detection. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2201.10323>
- [20] Azzedine Boukerche, Lining Zheng, and Omar Alfandi. 2020. Outlier detection: Methods, models, and classification. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 53, 3 (2020), 1–37.
- [21] Stephen Boyd, Corinna Cortes, Mehryar Mohri, and Ana Radovanovic. 2012. Accuracy at the top. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 25 (2012).
- [22] Mohammad Braei and Sebastian Wagner. 2020. Anomaly detection in univariate time-series: A survey on the state-of-the-art. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.00433* (2020).
- [23] Markus M Breunig, Hans-Peter Kriegel, Raymond T Ng, and Jörg Sander. 2000. LOF: identifying density-based local outliers. In *Proceedings of the 2000 ACM SIGMOD international conference on Management of data*. 93–104.
- [24] Klaus Brinker. 2003. Incorporating diversity in active learning with support vector machines. In *Proceedings of the 20th international conference on machine learning (ICML-03)*. 59–66.
- [25] Lukas Budach, Moritz Feuerpfeil, Nina Ihde, Andrea Nathansen, Nele Noack, Hendrik Patzlaff, Felix Naumann, and Hazar Harmouch. 2022. The effects of data quality on machine learning performance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.14529* (2022).
- [26] Samuel Budd, Emma C Robinson, and Bernhard Kainz. 2021. A survey on active learning and human-in-the-loop deep learning for medical image analysis. *Medical Image Analysis* 71 (2021), 102062.
- [27] Davide Cacciarelli and Murat Kulahci. 2024. Active learning for data streams: a survey. *Machine Learning* 113, 1 (2024), 185–239.
- [28] Xiangyong Cao, Jing Yao, Zongben Xu, and Deyu Meng. 2020. Hyperspectral image classification with convolutional neural network and active learning. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 58, 7 (2020), 4604–4616.
- [29] Mauro Castelli, Luca Manzoni, Tatiane Espindola, Aleš Popovič, and Andrea De Lorenzo. 2021. Generative adversarial networks for generating synthetic features for Wi-Fi signal quality. *Plos one* 16, 11 (2021), e0260308.
- [30] Nicolo Cesa-Bianchi, Claudio Gentile, and Luca Zaniboni. 2004. Worst-case analysis of selective sampling for linear-threshold algorithms. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 17 (2004).
- [31] Shayok Chakraborty. 2020. Asking the right questions to the right users: Active learning with imperfect oracles. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 34. 3365–3372.
- [32] Raghavendra Chalapathy and Sanjay Chawla. 2019. Deep learning for anomaly detection: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.03407* (2019).
- [33] Mathieu Chambefort, Raphaël Butez, Emilie Chautru, and Stephan Cléménçon. 2022. Improving the quality control of seismic data through active learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.06616* (2022).
- [34] Varun Chandola, Arindam Banerjee, and Vipin Kumar. 2009. Anomaly detection: A survey. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)* 41, 3 (2009), 1–58.

- [35] Nitesh V Chawla, Kevin W Bowyer, Lawrence O Hall, and W Philip Kegelmeyer. 2002. SMOTE: synthetic minority over-sampling technique. *Journal of artificial intelligence research* 16 (2002), 321–357.
- [36] Giuseppe Chicco, Davide; Jurman. 2020. The advantages of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) over F1 score and accuracy in binary classification evaluation. *BMC Genomics* 21, 1 (2020), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-019-6413-7>
- [37] Wei Chu, Martin Zinkevich, Lihong Li, Achint Thomas, and Belle Tseng. 2011. Unbiased Online Active Learning in Data Streams. In *Proceedings of the 17th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (San Diego, California, USA) (KDD '11)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 195203. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2020408.2020444>
- [38] Quang-Vinh Dang. 2020. Active learning for intrusion detection systems. In *2020 RIVF International Conference on Computing and Communication Technologies (RIVF)*. IEEE, 1–3.
- [39] T. T. Dang, Hyt Ngan, and L. Wei. 2015. Distance-based k-nearest neighbors outlier detection method in large-scale traffic data. In *IEEE International Conference on Digital Signal Processing*.
- [40] Shubhomoy Das, Md Rakibul Islam, Nitthilan Kannappan Jayakodi, and Janardhan Rao Doppa. 2019. Active Anomaly Detection via Ensembles: Insights, Algorithms, and Interpretability. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1901.08930>. *arXiv:1901.08930* (2019). [Online; accessed 27-Jan-2019].
- [41] Shubhomoy Das, Weng-Keen Wong, Thomas Dietterich, Alan Fern, and Andrew Emmott. 2016. Incorporating Expert Feedback into Active Anomaly Discovery. In *2016 IEEE 16th International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM)*. 853–858. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2016.0102>
- [42] Shubhomoy Das, Weng-Keen Wong, Alan Fern, Thomas G Dietterich, and Md Amran Siddiqui. 2017. Incorporating feedback into tree-based anomaly detection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.09441* (2017).
- [43] Jesse Davis and Mark Goadrich. 2006. The Relationship between Precision-Recall and ROC Curves. In *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Machine Learning (Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA) (ICML '06)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 233240. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1143844.1143874>
- [44] Jifei Deng, Jie Sun, Wen Peng, Dianhua Zhang, and Valeriy Vyatkin. 2022. Imbalanced multiclass classification with active learning in strip rolling process. *Knowledge-Based Systems* 255 (2022), 109754.
- [45] Debashree Devi, Saroj K Biswas, and Biswajit Purkayastha. 2020. A review on solution to class imbalance problem: Undersampling approaches. In *2020 international conference on computational performance evaluation (ComPE)*. IEEE, 626–631.
- [46] Jun Du and Charles X Ling. 2010. Active learning with human-like noisy oracle. In *2010 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*. IEEE, 797–802.
- [47] Murat Dundar, Balaji Krishnapuram, Jinbo Bi, and R Bharat Rao. 2007. Learning classifiers when the training data is not IID.. In *IJCAI*, Vol. 2007. 756–61.
- [48] Suparna Dutta and Monidipa Das. 2023. Remote sensing scene classification under scarcity of labelled samples: A survey of the state-of-the-arts. *Computers & Geosciences* (2023), 105295.
- [49] Dmitry Efimov, Di Xu, Luyang Kong, Alexey Nefedov, and Archana Anandakrishnan. 2020. Using generative adversarial networks to synthesize artificial financial datasets. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.02271* (2020).
- [50] Laila El Jiani, Sanaa El Filali, et al. 2022. Overcome medical image data scarcity by data augmentation techniques: A review. In *2022 International Conference on Microelectronics (ICM)*. IEEE, 21–24.
- [51] Ahmed K Elmagarmid, Panagiotis G Ipeirotis, and Vassilios S Verykios. 2006. Duplicate record detection: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on knowledge and data engineering* 19, 1 (2006), 1–16.
- [52] Justin Engelmann and Stefan Lessmann. 2021. Conditional Wasserstein GAN-based oversampling of tabular data for imbalanced learning. *Expert Systems with Applications* 174 (2021), 114582.
- [53] Seyda Ertekin, Jian Huang, Leon Bottou, and Lee Giles. 2007. Learning on the Border: Active Learning in Imbalanced Data Classification. In *Proceedings of the Sixteenth ACM Conference on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (Lisbon, Portugal) (CIKM '07)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 127136. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1321440.1321461>
- [54] Seyda Ertekin, Jian Huang, and C Lee Giles. 2007. Active learning for class imbalance problem. In *Proceedings of the 30th annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval*. 823–824.
- [55] Eleazar Eskin. 2000. Detecting errors within a corpus using anomaly detection. In *1st Meeting of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*.

- [56] Conor Fahy, Shengxiang Yang, and Mario Gongora. 2022. Scarcity of labels in non-stationary data streams: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 55, 2 (2022), 1–39.
- [57] Meng Fang, Yuan Li, and Trevor Cohn. 2017. Learning how to active learn: A deep reinforcement learning approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.02383* (2017).
- [58] Abolfazl Farahani, Sahar Voghoei, Khaled Rasheed, and Hamid R Arabnia. 2021. A brief review of domain adaptation. *Advances in data science and information engineering: proceedings from ICDATA 2020 and IKE 2020* (2021), 877–894.
- [59] Alvaro Figueira and Bruno Vaz. 2022. Survey on synthetic data generation, evaluation methods and GANs. *Mathematics* 10, 15 (2022), 2733.
- [60] Benoît Fréney and Michel Verleysen. 2013. Classification in the presence of label noise: a survey. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems* 25, 5 (2013), 845–869.
- [61] Robert M French. 1999. Catastrophic forgetting in connectionist networks. *Trends in cognitive sciences* 3, 4 (1999), 128–135.
- [62] Alexander Freytag, Erik Rodner, and Joachim Denzler. 2014. Selecting influential examples: Active learning with expected model output changes. In *Computer Vision—ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich, Switzerland, September 6-12, 2014, Proceedings, Part IV 13*. Springer, 562–577.
- [63] Yifan Fu, Xingquan Zhu, and Bin Li. 2013. A survey on instance selection for active learning. *Knowledge and information systems* 35 (2013), 249–283.
- [64] Yarin Gal, Riashat Islam, and Zoubin Ghahramani. 2017. Deep bayesian active learning with image data. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 1183–1192.
- [65] Joao Gama, Pedro Medas, Gladys Castillo, and Pedro Rodrigues. 2004. Learning with drift detection. In *Advances in Artificial Intelligence—SBIA 2004: 17th Brazilian Symposium on Artificial Intelligence, Sao Luis, Maranhao, Brazil, September 29-October 1, 2004. Proceedings 17*. Springer, 286–295.
- [66] Joao Gama, Raquel Sebastiao, and Pedro Pereira Rodrigues. 2013. On evaluating stream learning algorithms. *Machine learning* 90 (2013), 317–346.
- [67] Guojun Gan and Michael Kwok-Po Ng. 2017. K-means clustering with outlier removal. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 90 (2017), 8–14.
- [68] Aurélien Géron. 2022. *Hands-on machine learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- [69] Mohsen Ghassemi, Anand D Sarwate, and Rebecca N Wright. 2016. Differentially private online active learning with applications to anomaly detection. In *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security*. 117–128.
- [70] Markus Goldstein. 2012. FastLOF: An expectation-maximization based local outlier detection algorithm. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR2012)*. IEEE, 2282–2285.
- [71] Ian Goodfellow, Jean Pouget-Abadie, Mehdi Mirza, Bing Xu, David Warde-Farley, Sherjil Ozair, Aaron Courville, and Yoshua Bengio. 2014. Generative adversarial nets. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 27 (2014).
- [72] Venkat Gudivada, Amy Apon, and Junhua Ding. 2017. Data quality considerations for big data and machine learning: Going beyond data cleaning and transformations. *International Journal on Advances in Software* 10, 1 (2017), 1–20.
- [73] Sudipto Guha, Nina Mishra, Gourav Roy, and Okke Schrijvers. 2016. Robust random cut forest based anomaly detection on streams. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2712–2721.
- [74] Chuan Guo, Geoff Pleiss, Yu Sun, and Kilian Q Weinberger. 2017. On calibration of modern neural networks. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 1321–1330.
- [75] Nitin Gupta, Shashank Mujumdar, Hima Patel, Satoshi Masuda, Naveen Panwar, Sambaran Bandyopadhyay, Sameep Mehta, Shanmukha Guttula, Shazia Afzal, Ruhi Sharma Mittal, and Vitobha Munigala. 2021. *Data Quality for Machine Learning Tasks*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 40404041.
- [76] Nico Görnitz, Marius Kloft, Konrad Rieck, and Ulf Brefeld. 2013. Toward supervised anomaly detection. *The Journal of artificial intelligence research* 46 (2013), 235–262.
- [77] Robbie Haertel, Eric Ringger, Kevin Seppi, James Carroll, and Peter McClanahan. 2008. Assessing the costs of sampling methods in active learning for annotation. In *Proceedings of ACL-08: HLT, Short Papers*. 65–68.

- [78] Bohnishikha Halder, Md Manjur Ahmed, Toshiyuki Amagasa, Nor Ashidi Mat Isa, Rahat Hossain Faisal, and Md Mostafijur Rahman. 2022. Missing information in imbalanced data stream: fuzzy adaptive imputation approach. *Applied Intelligence* (2022), 1–23.
- [79] Alon Halevy, Peter Norvig, and Fernando Pereira. 2009. The unreasonable effectiveness of data. *IEEE intelligent systems* 24, 2 (2009), 8–12.
- [80] Steve Hanneke. 2013. A statistical theory of active learning. *Foundations and Trends in Machine Learning* (2013), 1–212.
- [81] Shuji Hao, Jing Lu, Peilin Zhao, Chi Zhang, Steven CH Hoi, and Chunyan Miao. 2017. Second-order online active learning and its applications. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 30, 7 (2017), 1338–1351.
- [82] Sahand Hariri, Matias Carrasco Kind, and Robert J Brunner. 2019. Extended isolation forest. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 33, 4 (2019), 1479–1489.
- [83] Ville Hautamaki, Ismo Karkkainen, and Pasi Franti. 2004. Outlier detection using k-nearest neighbour graph. In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pattern Recognition, 2004. ICPR 2004.*, Vol. 3. IEEE, 430–433.
- [84] Douglas M Hawkins. 1980. *Identification of outliers*. Vol. 11. Springer.
- [85] Victoria Hodge and Jim Austin. 2004. A survey of outlier detection methodologies. *Artificial intelligence review* 22 (2004), 85–126.
- [86] T Ryan Hoens, Robi Polikar, and Nitesh V Chawla. 2012. Learning from streaming data with concept drift and imbalance: an overview. *Progress in Artificial Intelligence* 1 (2012), 89–101.
- [87] Boshuang Huang, Kobi Cohen, and Qing Zhao. 2018. Active anomaly detection in heterogeneous processes. *IEEE Transactions on information theory* 65, 4 (2018), 2284–2301.
- [88] Chengqiang Huang, Yulei Wu, Yuan Zuo, Ke Pei, and Geyong Min. 2018. Towards experienced anomaly detector through reinforcement learning. In *Thirty-Second AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*.
- [89] ISO. 2008. ISO/IEC 25012-Software engineering: Software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE). *Data quality model* (2008).
- [90] Wen Jin, Anthony KH Tung, Jiawei Han, and Wei Wang. 2006. Ranking outliers using symmetric neighborhood relationship. In *Pacific-Asia conference on knowledge discovery and data mining*. Springer, 577–593.
- [91] Justin M Johnson and Taghi M Khoshgoftaar. 2019. Survey on deep learning with class imbalance. *Journal of Big Data* 6, 1 (2019), 1–54.
- [92] Tero Karras, Timo Aila, Samuli Laine, and Jaakko Lehtinen. 2017. Progressive growing of gans for improved quality, stability, and variation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.10196* (2017).
- [93] Harsurinder Kaur, Husanbir Singh Pannu, and Avleen Kaur Malhi. 2019. A systematic review on imbalanced data challenges in machine learning: Applications and solutions. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 52, 4 (2019), 1–36.
- [94] Diederik P Kingma and Max Welling. 2013. Auto-encoding variational bayes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6114* (2013).
- [95] Eduard T Klapwijk, Ferdi Van De Kamp, Mara Van Der Meulen, Sabine Peters, and Lara M Wierenga. 2019. Qoala-T: A supervised-learning tool for quality control of FreeSurfer segmented MRI data. *Neuroimage* 189 (2019), 116–129.
- [96] Edwin M Knox and Raymond T Ng. 1998. Algorithms for mining distancebased outliers in large datasets. In *Proceedings of the international conference on very large data bases*. Citeseer, 392–403.
- [97] Naveen Kodali, Jacob Abernethy, James Hays, and Zsolt Kira. 2017. On convergence and stability of gans. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.07215* (2017).
- [98] Bartosz Krawczyk, Leandro L Minku, João Gama, Jerzy Stefanowski, and Michał Woźniak. 2017. Ensemble learning for data stream analysis: A survey. *Information Fusion* 37 (2017), 132–156.
- [99] Punit Kumar and Atul Gupta. 2020. Active learning query strategies for classification, regression, and clustering: a survey. *Journal of Computer Science and Technology* 35 (2020), 913–945.
- [100] Donghwoon Kwon, Hyunjoo Kim, Jinh Kim, Sang C Suh, Ikkyun Kim, and Kuinam J Kim. 2019. A survey of deep learning-based network anomaly detection. *Cluster Computing* 22 (2019), 949–961.

- [101] Tze Leung Lai. 1995. Sequential changepoint detection in quality control and dynamical systems. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)* 57, 4 (1995), 613–644.
- [102] Longyuan Li, Junchi Yan, Haiyang Wang, and Yaohui Jin. 2021. Anomaly Detection of Time Series With Smoothness-Inducing Sequential Variational Auto-Encoder. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems* 32, 3 (2021), 1177–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2020.2980749>
- [103] Weixin Liang, Girmaw Abebe Tadesse, Daniel Ho, L Fei-Fei, Matei Zaharia, Ce Zhang, and James Zou. 2022. Advances, challenges and opportunities in creating data for trustworthy AI. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 4, 8 (2022), 669–677.
- [104] Zicheng Liao, Yizhou Yu, and Baoquan Chen. 2010. Anomaly detection in GPS data based on visual analytics. In *2010 IEEE Symposium on Visual Analytics Science and Technology*. IEEE, 51–58.
- [105] Ray Liere and Prasad Tadepalli. 1996. The use of active learning in text categorization. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Symposium on Machine Learning in Information Access*. Citeseer.
- [106] Fei Tony Liu, Kai Ming Ting, and Zhi-Hua Zhou. 2008. Isolation forest. In *2008 eighth IEEE international conference on data mining*. IEEE, 413–422.
- [107] Ming-Yu Liu and Oncel Tuzel. 2016. Coupled generative adversarial networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 29 (2016), 469–477.
- [108] Sanmin Liu, Shan Xue, Jia Wu, Chuan Zhou, Jian Yang, Zhao Li, and Jie Cao. 2021. Online active learning for drifting data streams. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems* (2021).
- [109] Manuel Lopes, Francisco Melo, and Luis Montesano. 2009. Active learning for reward estimation in inverse reinforcement learning. In *Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases: European Conference, ECML PKDD 2009, Bled, Slovenia, September 7-11, 2009, Proceedings, Part II 20*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 31–46.
- [110] Mohammad Lotfollahi, Mohsen Naghipourfar, Fabian J Theis, and F Alexander Wolf. 2020. Conditional out-of-distribution generation for unpaired data using transfer VAE. *Bioinformatics* 36, Supplement_2 (2020), i610–i617.
- [111] Chen Change Loy, Tao Xiang, and Shaogang Gong. [n. d.]. Stream-Based Active Unusual Event Detection. In *Computer Vision ACCV 2010 (Lecture Notes in Computer Science)*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 161–175.
- [112] Jie Lu, Anjin Liu, Fan Dong, Feng Gu, Joao Gama, and Guangquan Zhang. 2018. Learning under concept drift: A review. *IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering* 31, 12 (2018), 2346–2363.
- [113] Yingzhou Lu, Huazheng Wang, and Wenqi Wei. 2023. Machine Learning for Synthetic Data Generation: a Review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.04062* (2023).
- [114] Batta Mahesh. 2020. Machine learning algorithms—a review. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR).[Internet]* 9 (2020), 381–386.
- [115] Elisa Marcelli, Tommaso Barbariol, and Gian Antonio Susto. 2022. Active Learning-based Isolation Forest (ALIF): Enhancing Anomaly Detection in Decision Support Systems. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.03934* (2022).
- [116] Ninareh Mehrabi, Fred Morstatter, Nripsuta Saxena, Kristina Lerman, and Aram Galstyan. 2021. A survey on bias and fairness in machine learning. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)* 54, 6 (2021), 1–35.
- [117] Sebastian Mieruch, Serdar Demirel, Simona Simoncelli, Reiner Schlitzer, and Steffen Seitz. 2021. SalaciaML: A Deep Learning Approach for Supporting Ocean Data Quality Control. *Frontiers in Marine Science* (2021).
- [118] Mehdi Mirza and Simon Osindero. 2014. Conditional generative adversarial nets. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1411.1784* (2014).
- [119] Douglas C Montgomery. 2019. *Introduction to statistical quality control*. John Wiley & sons.
- [120] Nour Moustafa and Jill Slay. 2015. UNSW-NB15: a comprehensive data set for network intrusion detection systems (UNSW-NB15 network data set). In *2015 Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)*. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MilCIS.2015.7348942>
- [121] Stephen Mussmann and Percy Liang. 2018. On the relationship between data efficiency and error for uncertainty sampling. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*. PMLR, 3674–3682.
- [122] Mona Nashaat, Aindrila Ghosh, James Miller, Shaikh Quader, Chad Marston, and Jean-Francois Puget. 2018. Hybridization of active learning and data programming for labeling large industrial datasets. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*. IEEE, 46–55.

- [123] Ali Bou Nassif, Manar Abu Talib, Qassim Nasir, and Fatima Mohamad Dakalbab. 2021. Machine Learning for Anomaly Detection: A Systematic Review. *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), 78658–78700. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3083060>
- [124] Andrew Y Ng, Stuart J Russell, et al. 2000. Algorithms for inverse reinforcement learning.. In *Icml*, Vol. 1. 2.
- [125] Christopher Nixon, Mohamed Sedky, and Mohamed Hassan. 2021. Salad: An exploration of split active learning based unsupervised network data stream anomaly detection using autoencoders. (2021).
- [126] Min-hwan Oh and Garud Iyengar. 2019. Sequential anomaly detection using inverse reinforcement learning. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & data mining*. 1480–1490.
- [127] Kalia Orphanou, Jahna Otterbacher, Styliani Kleanthous, Khuyagbaatar Batsuren, Fausto Giunchiglia, Veronika Bogina, Avital Shulner Tal, Alan Hartman, and Tsvi Kuflik. 2022. Mitigating Bias in Algorithmic Systems: A Fish-Eye View. *Comput. Surveys* 55, 5 (2022), 1–37.
- [128] Rajendra Pamula, Jatindra Kumar Deka, and Sukumar Nandi. 2011. An outlier detection method based on clustering. In *2011 Second International Conference on Emerging Applications of Information Technology*. IEEE, 253–256.
- [129] Lujia Pan, Jianfeng Zhang, Patrick P.C. Lee, Marcus Kalander, Junjian Ye, and Pinghui Wang. 2020. Proactive microwave link anomaly detection in cellular data networks. *Computer Networks* 167 (2020), 106969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106969>
- [130] Guansong Pang, Chunhua Shen, Longbing Cao, and Anton Van Den Hengel. 2021. Deep learning for anomaly detection: A review. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)* 54, 2 (2021), 1–38.
- [131] Guansong Pang, Chunhua Shen, and Anton van den Hengel. 2019. Deep anomaly detection with deviation networks. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery & data mining*. 353–362.
- [132] Kunkun Pang, Mingzhi Dong, Yang Wu, and Timothy Hospedales. 2018. Meta-learning transferable active learning policies by deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.04798* (2018).
- [133] Gilberto Pastorello, Dan Gunter, Housen Chu, Danielle Christianson, Carlo Trotta, Eleonora Canfora, Boris Faybisenko, You-Wei Cheah, Norm Beekwilder, Stephen Chan, et al. 2017. Hunting data rogues at scale: Data quality control for observational data in research infrastructures. In *2017 IEEE 13th International Conference on e-Science (e-Science)*. IEEE, 446–447.
- [134] Tomáš Pevný. 2016. Loda: Lightweight on-line detector of anomalies. *Machine Learning* 102, 2 (2016), 275–304.
- [135] Marco AF Pimentel, David A Clifton, Lei Clifton, and Lionel Tarassenko. 2014. A review of novelty detection. *Signal processing* 99 (2014), 215–249.
- [136] Leo L Pipino, Yang W Lee, and Richard Y Wang. 2002. Data quality assessment. *Commun. ACM* 45, 4 (2002), 211–218.
- [137] Antonella D Pontoriero, Giovanna Nordio, Rubaida Easmin, Alessio Giacomel, Barbara Santangelo, Sameer Jahuar, Ilaria Bonoldi, Maria Rogdaki, Federico Turkheimer, Oliver Howes, et al. 2021. Automated Data Quality Control in FDOPA brain PET Imaging using Deep Learning. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* (2021), 106239.
- [138] Maria Priestley, Fionntán ODonnell, and Elena Simperl. 2023. A survey of data quality requirements that matter in ML development pipelines. *ACM Journal of Data and Information Quality* (2023).
- [139] Piyush Rai, Avishek Saha, Hal Daumé III, and Suresh Venkatasubramanian. 2010. Domain adaptation meets active learning. In *Proceedings of the NAACL HLT 2010 Workshop on Active Learning for Natural Language Processing*. 27–32.
- [140] Pengzhen Ren, Yun Xiao, Xiaojun Chang, Po-Yao Huang, Zhihui Li, Brij B Gupta, Xiaojiang Chen, and Xin Wang. 2021. A survey of deep active learning. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)* 54, 9 (2021), 1–40.
- [141] Nicholas Roy and Andrew McCallum. 2001. Toward optimal active learning through monte carlo estimation of error reduction. *ICML, Williamstown* 2 (2001), 441–448.
- [142] Stefania Russo, Moritz Lürig, Wenjin Hao, Blake Matthews, and Kris Villez. 2020. Active learning for anomaly detection in environmental data. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 134 (2020), 104869.
- [143] Carlos Sáez, Nekane Romero, J Alberto Conejero, and Juan M García-Gómez. 2021. Potential limitations in COVID-19 machine learning due to data source variability: A case study in the nCov2019 dataset. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 28, 2 (2021), 360–364.

- [144] Takaya Saito and Marc Rehmsmeier. 2015. The precision-recall plot is more informative than the ROC plot when evaluating binary classifiers on imbalanced datasets. *PLoS one* 10, 3 (2015), e0118432.
- [145] Vignesh Sampath, Iñaki Maurtua, Juan Jose Aguilar Martin, and Aitor Gutierrez. 2021. A survey on generative adversarial networks for imbalance problems in computer vision tasks. *Journal of big Data* 8 (2021), 1–59.
- [146] Andrew I Schein and Lyle H Ungar. 2007. Active learning for logistic regression: an evaluation. *Machine Learning* 68, 3 (2007), 235–265.
- [147] Sebastian Schmidl, Phillip Wenig, and Thorsten Papenbrock. 2022. Anomaly detection in time series: a comprehensive evaluation. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 15, 9 (2022), 1779–1797.
- [148] Christopher Schröder and Andreas Niekler. 2020. A survey of active learning for text classification using deep neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2008.07267* (2020).
- [149] Christopher Schröder, Andreas Niekler, and Martin Potthast. 2021. Uncertainty-based query strategies for active learning with transformers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.05687* (2021).
- [150] Ozan Sener and Silvio Savarese. 2017. Active learning for convolutional neural networks: A core-set approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.00489* (2017).
- [151] Burr Settles. 2009. Active learning literature survey. (2009).
- [152] Burr Settles. 2011. From theories to queries: Active learning in practice. In *Active learning and experimental design workshop in conjunction with AISTATS 2010*. JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings, 1–18.
- [153] Burr Settles, Mark Craven, and Lewis Friedland. 2008. Active learning with real annotation costs. In *Proceedings of the NIPS workshop on cost-sensitive learning*, Vol. 1. Vancouver, CA:.
- [154] Burr Settles, Mark Craven, and Soumya Ray. 2007. Multiple-instance active learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 20 (2007).
- [155] H. S. Seung, M. Opper, and H. Sompolinsky. 1992. Query by Committee. In *Proceedings of the Fifth Annual Workshop on Computational Learning Theory* (Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA) (COLT '92). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 287294. <https://doi.org/10.1145/130385.130417>
- [156] Shweta Sharma, Anjana Gosain, and Shreya Jain. 2022. A review of the oversampling techniques in class imbalance problem. In *International Conference on Innovative Computing and Communications: Proceedings of ICICC 2021, Volume 1*. Springer, 459–472.
- [157] Haotian Shi, Haoren Wang, Chengjin Qin, Liqun Zhao, and Chengliang Liu. 2020. An incremental learning system for atrial fibrillation detection based on transfer learning and active learning. *Computer methods and programs in biomedicine* 187 (2020), 105219.
- [158] Fatimah Sidi, Payam Hassany Shariat Panahy, Lilly Suriani Affendey, Marzanah A. Jabar, Hamidah Ibrahim, and Aida Mustapha. 2012. Data quality: A survey of data quality dimensions. In *2012 International Conference on Information Retrieval & Knowledge Management*. 300–304. <https://doi.org/10.1109/InfRKM.2012.6204995>
- [159] Simona Simoncelli, Paolo Oliveri, Gelsomina Mattia, and Volodymyr Myroshnychenko. 2020. SeaDataCloud Temperature and Salinity Historical Data Collection for the Mediterranean Sea (Version 2). (2020).
- [160] Ikbal Taleb, Mohamed Adel Serhani, and Rachida Dssouli. 2018. Big data quality: A survey. In *2018 IEEE International Congress on Big Data (BigData Congress)*. IEEE, 166–173.
- [161] Jian Tang, Zhixiang Chen, Ada Wai chee Fu, and David Cheung. 2001. A Robust Outlier Detection Scheme for Large Data Sets. In *In 6th Pacific-Asia Conf. on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. 6–8.
- [162] Youbao Tang, Jinzheng Cai, Le Lu, Adam P Harrison, Ke Yan, Jing Xiao, Lin Yang, and Ronald M Summers. 2018. CT image enhancement using stacked generative adversarial networks and transfer learning for lesion segmentation improvement. In *International Workshop on Machine Learning in Medical Imaging*. Springer, 46–54.
- [163] Alexander G Tartakovsky, Aleksey S Polunchenko, and Grigory Sokolov. 2012. Efficient computer network anomaly detection by changepoint detection methods. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing* 7, 1 (2012), 4–11.
- [164] Hui Yie Teh, Andreas W. Kempa-Liehr, and Kevin I-Kai Wang. 2020. Sensor data quality: a systematic review. *Journal of big data* 7, 1 (2020), 1–49.
- [165] Fadi Thabtah, Suhel Hammoud, Firuz Kamalov, and Amanda Gonsalves. 2020. Data imbalance in classification: Experimental evaluation. *Information Sciences* 513 (2020), 429–441.

- [166] Siddharth Thakur, Jaytrilok Choudhary, and Dharendra Pratap Singh. 2021. A survey on missing values handling methods for time series data. In *Intelligent Systems: Proceedings of SCIS 2021*. Springer, 435–443.
- [167] Holger Trittenbach, Adrian Englhardt, and Klemens Böhm. 2021. An overview and a benchmark of active learning for outlier detection with one-class classifiers. *Expert Systems with Applications* 168 (2021), 114372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.114372>
- [168] Gido M van de Ven, Tinne Tuytelaars, and Andreas S Tolias. 2022. Three types of incremental learning. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 4, 12 (2022), 1185–1197.
- [169] Jesper E Van Engelen and Holger H Hoos. 2020. A survey on semi-supervised learning. *Machine learning* 109, 2 (2020), 373–440.
- [170] Susana M Vieira, Uzay Kaymak, and João MC Sousa. 2010. Cohen’s kappa coefficient as a performance measure for feature selection. In *International conference on fuzzy systems*. IEEE, 1–8.
- [171] Zhiqiang Wan, Yazhou Zhang, and Haibo He. 2017. Variational autoencoder based synthetic data generation for imbalanced learning. In *2017 IEEE symposium series on computational intelligence (SSCI)*. IEEE, 1–7.
- [172] Meng Wang and Xian-Sheng Hua. 2011. Active learning in multimedia annotation and retrieval: A survey. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology (TIST)* 2, 2 (2011), 1–21.
- [173] Shuo Wang, Leandro L Minku, and Xin Yao. 2018. A systematic study of online class imbalance learning with concept drift. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems* 29, 10 (2018), 4802–4821.
- [174] Wenlu Wang, Pengfei Chen, Yibin Xu, and Zilong He. 2022. Active-MTSAD: Multivariate Time Series Anomaly Detection With Active Learning. In *2022 52nd Annual IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks (DSN)*. IEEE, 263–274.
- [175] Xiaogang Wang, Xiaoxu Ma, and W Eric L Grimson. 2008. Unsupervised activity perception in crowded and complicated scenes using hierarchical bayesian models. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 31, 3 (2008), 539–555.
- [176] Yao Wang, Zhaowei Wang, Zejun Xie, Nengwen Zhao, Junjie Chen, Wenchi Zhang, Kaixin Sui, and Dan Pei. 2020. Practical and white-box anomaly detection through unsupervised and active learning. In *2020 29th international conference on computer communications and networks (ICCCN)*. IEEE, 1–9.
- [177] Gary M Weiss and Foster Provost. 2003. Learning when training data are costly: The effect of class distribution on tree induction. *Journal of artificial intelligence research* 19 (2003), 315–354.
- [178] Ashenafi Zebene Woldaregay, Eirik Årsand, Taxiarchis Botsis, David Albers, Lena Mamykina, and Gunnar Hartvigsen. 2019. Data-driven blood glucose pattern classification and anomalies detection: machine-learning applications in type 1 diabetes. *Journal of medical Internet research* 21, 5 (2019), e11030.
- [179] Tong Wu and Jorge Ortiz. 2021. Rlad: Time series anomaly detection through reinforcement learning and active learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.00543* (2021).
- [180] Yanping Yang, Guangzhi Ma, et al. 2010. Ensemble-based active learning for class imbalance problem. *Journal of Biomedical Science and Engineering* 3, 10 (2010), 1022.
- [181] Yang Yang, Da-Wei Zhou, De-Chuan Zhan, Hui Xiong, and Yuan Jiang. 2019. Adaptive deep models for incremental learning: Considering capacity scalability and sustainability. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*. 74–82.
- [182] Donggeun Yoo and In So Kweon. 2019. Learning loss for active learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 93–102.
- [183] Mengran Yu and Shiliang Sun. 2020. Policy-based reinforcement learning for time series anomaly detection. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 95 (2020), 103919.
- [184] Hang Zhang, Weike Liu, Jicheng Shan, and Qingbao Liu. 2018. Online active learning paired ensemble for concept drift and class imbalance. *IEEE Access* 6 (2018), 73815–73828.
- [185] Liumei Zhang, Baoyu Tan, Tianshi Liu, and Xiaoqun Sun. 2019. Classification study for the imbalanced data based on Biased-SVM and the modified over-sampling algorithm. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 1237. IOP Publishing, 022052.
- [186] Xiaoxuan Zhang, Tianbao Yang, and Padmini Srinivasan. 2016. Online asymmetric active learning with imbalanced data. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. 2055–2064.

- [187] Peilin Zhao and Steven C.H. Hoi. 2013. Cost-Sensitive Online Active Learning with Application to Malicious URL Detection. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (Chicago, Illinois, USA) (*KDD '13*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 919927. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2487575.2487647>
- [188] Dequan Zheng, Fenghuan Li, and Tiejun Zhao. 2016. Self-adaptive statistical process control for anomaly detection in time series. *Expert Systems with Applications* 57 (2016), 324–336.
- [189] Xingquan Zhu, Peng Zhang, Xiaodong Lin, and Yong Shi. 2007. Active learning from data streams. In *Seventh IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM 2007)*. IEEE, 757–762.
- [190] Yizhe Zhu, Martin Renqiang Min, Asim Kadav, and Hans Peter Graf. 2020. S3vae: Self-supervised sequential vae for representation disentanglement and data generation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 6538–6547.
- [191] Amir Ziai. 2021. Active learning for network intrusion detection. *Data Science: Theory, Algorithms, and Applications* (2021), 3–14.
- [192] Indrè Žliobaitė, Albert Bifet, Bernhard Pfahringer, and Geoffrey Holmes. 2013. Active learning with drifting streaming data. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems* 25, 1 (2013), 27–39.
- [193] Indrė Žliobaitė, Mykola Pechenizkiy, and Joao Gama. 2016. An overview of concept drift applications. *Big data analysis: new algorithms for a new society* (2016), 91–114.